

PHILOSOPHICAL TRANSACTIONS OF THE ROYAL SOCIETY B

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

The influence of changing fire regimes on specialised plant- animal interactions

Journal:	<i>Philosophical Transactions B</i>
Manuscript ID	RSTB-2023-0448.R2
Article Type:	Review
Date Submitted by the Author:	n/a
Complete List of Authors:	Charles, Felicity; The University of Queensland Faculty of Science, School of the Environment Reside, April; The University of Queensland Faculty of Science, School of the Environment Smith, Annabel; The University of Queensland Faculty of Science, School of the Environment
Issue Code (this should have already been entered and appear below the blue box, but please contact the Editorial Office if it is not present):	FIREREG
Subject:	Ecology < BIOLOGY, Evolution < BIOLOGY
Keywords:	ecological specialisation, evolutionary ecology, feedbacks, fire ecology, global change, niche breadth

SCHOLARONE™
Manuscripts

Author-supplied statements

Relevant information will appear here if provided.

Ethics

Does your article include research that required ethical approval or permits?:

This article does not present research with ethical considerations

Statement (if applicable):

CUST_IF_YES_ETHICS :No data available.

Data

It is a condition of publication that data, code and materials supporting your paper are made publicly available. Does your paper present new data?:

My paper has no data

Statement (if applicable):

CUST_IF_YES_DATA :No data available.

Conflict of interest

I/We declare we have no competing interests

Statement (if applicable):

CUST_STATE_CONFLICT :No data available.

Use of AI

Please provide a statement of any use of AI technology in the preparation of the paper.

No, we have not used AI-assisted technologies in creating this article

CUST_IF_YES_DECLARATION_OF_AI_USE :No data available.

The influence of changing fire regimes on specialised plant-animal interactions

Felicity E. Charles^{1*} 0000-0002-7241-2720

April E. Reside¹ 0000-0002-0760-9527

Annabel L. Smith¹ 0000-0002-1201-8713

¹School of the Environment, The University of Queensland, Gatton, 4343, QLD, Australia

*Correspondence: f.charles@uq.edu.au

Abstract

Ecological effects of changing fire regimes are well documented for plant and animal populations, but less is known about how fire influences, and is influenced by, specialised plant-animal interactions. In this review, we identified mutualistic (pollination, seed dispersal, and food provision), commensal (habitat provision) and antagonistic (seed predation, herbivory, and parasitism) plant-animal interactions from fire-prone ecosystems. We focused on specialised interactions where a single genus depended on one to two genera in a single family of plant or animal. We categorised the plant partner's post-fire reproductive mode to assess the likely outcome of changing fire regimes on ecological functions provided by these interactions. Traits underlying specialisation in fire-prone ecosystems for plants were: post-fire reproductive mode, time to maturity, morphology, and phenology; and, for animals: dispersal, specialised organs, nesting and egg deposition substrates, plant consumption behaviours, and pollinator behaviours. Finally, we identified a number of cases where stabilising feedbacks maintained plant-animal interactions under natural fire regimes. Potential reinforcing feedbacks were also identified, but were more likely to happen abruptly and result in collapse of the plant-animal partnership, or partner switching. Our synthesis reveals how fire regime changes impact fire-dependent specialist plant-animal interactions and potentially drive eco-evolutionary dynamics in fire-prone ecosystems globally.

Keywords: ecological specialisation, evolutionary ecology, feedbacks, fire ecology, global change, niche breadth

33 **Introduction**

34
35 Fire plays an important role in the evolution of plant and animal traits and ecological function
36 [1-3] but contemporary changes in fire regimes are driving global biodiversity declines [4-6].
37 Rapid changes in land use and climate are increasing the frequency, intensity, and duration of
38 fires in many parts of the world, especially at mid- to high-latitudes [7-9]. In other regions, a
39 reduction in cultural or prescribed burning, coupled with high-biomass invasive species [10,
40 11] has changed spatial patterns of wildfire risk [12, 13]. These changes have led to
41 increasing large, catastrophic wildfires in many regions globally [14, 15]. How species and
42 ecosystems will respond to these rapid changes is not well known, especially for specialists
43 that have specific resource requirements (e.g., a single genus of plant or animal relying on
44 one to two genera within a single family [16, 17]) [18, 19].

45
46 In contrast to rapid contemporary changes, the ecological and evolutionary effects of
47 historical fire regimes have been well documented for a range of plant and animal
48 populations and ecological communities [5, 20-22]. Spatio-temporal patterns of biodiversity
49 in fire-prone ecosystems are shaped by the interplay between plant and animal functional
50 traits, life history parameters, environmental variation, and fire regimes (characterised by
51 frequency, severity, size, and season) [21-24]. In fire prone ecosystems, plant population
52 dynamics are influenced by morphological traits such as flammability [25, 26], branch
53 retention or shedding [25], and bark thickness [25]; reproductive traits including post-fire
54 reproductive mode, post-fire flowering, and serotiny [22, 27, 28]; and life history parameters
55 including survival [27] and recruitment [29-31] rates. For animals, key factors influencing
56 fire-related population dynamics include survival, habitat requirements, movement, dispersal,
57 and behaviour (e.g., taking refuge in burrows or rock fissures) [23, 27, 28]. A vast body of
58 literature has documented how fire-induced changes in plant populations affects animals,
59 such as structural changes in post-fire vegetation driving succession in animal abundance [32-
60 35]. Similarly well-known are the directional effects of animals on vegetation structure and
61 how these influence, and are influenced by, fire (e.g., grazing animals modulating the fire
62 regime through their influence on vegetation structure [34, 36]). Less is known, however,
63 about how variation in fire regimes affects specialised plant-animal interactions, where one
64 genus is dependent on one to two genera in a single plant or animal family for pollination,
65 dispersal, food, or habitat (e.g., [37]).

66

1
2
3 67 Understanding the effects of fire regimes on specialist interactions is important for at least
4
5 68 two reasons. First, theory predicts that, while generalists have wider environmental tolerances
6
7 69 [38] and often complex genetic structure [39-41], specialists may evolve faster than
8
9 70 generalists because they have a simpler 'fitness landscape' for a given environmental niche
10
11 71 [42-44]. Specialists can more rapidly fix alleles that increase their fitness for a given niche,
12
13 72 while generalists require longer time scales [42]. Environmental variability can, therefore,
14
15 73 pose a stronger selection pressure on specialists than generalists due to their restricted niche
16
17 74 [45, 46]. In the context of rapidly changing fire regimes, eco-evolutionary feedbacks might,
18
19 75 therefore, be stronger for specialist, than generalist, interactions [42, 47, 48].
20
21 76

22 77 The second reason why understanding fire effects on specialist plant-animal interactions is
23
24 78 important is that specialists have a higher risk of extinction under rapid environmental change
25
26 79 than generalists [19, 49, 50]. Although specialists have potential for rapid adaptation, their
27
28 80 ability to do so depends on how their adaptation potential co-varies with the direction, scale,
29
30 81 and rate of environmental change [42, 46, 47]. Furthermore, the interaction type (i.e.,
31
32 82 mutualism, commensalism, or antagonism) could influence the evolutionary outcome and,
33
34 83 thus, the risk of extinction [51, 52]. For example, co-dependencies between interactors in
35
36 84 mutualisms might make both interactors more susceptible to extinctions [53]. 'Partner
37
38 85 switching', whereby one interaction partner switches to interact with a new interaction
39
40 86 partner [51]; and changes in interaction type, such as commensalisms or mutualisms evolving
41
42 87 into antagonisms [51, 52], have been documented under rapid environmental change.
43
44 88 Whether this has happened for specialised interactions in the context of changing fire regimes
45
46 89 is largely unknown. Thus, gaining greater understanding of how changing fire regimes will
47
48 90 impact specialist interactions and how these changes might feed back into ecological changes
49
50 91 will improve our ability to manage ecosystems.
51
52 92

53 93 In this study we examined the influence of fire regimes on specialised plant-animal
54
55 94 interactions. We first compiled a database of specialised plant-animal interactions from fire-
56
57 95 prone ecosystems to identify cases where changing fire regimes might drive eco-evolutionary
58
59 96 dynamics. We defined specialist interactions as those involving a single genus of plant or
60
61 97 animal that was specialised on one to two genera within a single family of plant or animal
62
63 98 [16, 17]. In some cases, a species was identified as being generalist across its distributional
64
65 99 range but specialised in a particular ecosystem where its main resource was abundant (e.g.,
66
67 100 50% of their diet was comprised of a single family of plants [54]) [55, 56]. We included such

1
2
3 101 cases in our review. We characterised plant-animal interactions as mutualistic, commensal, or
4
5 102 antagonistic [52, 57] and then applied a framework for classifying plant post-fire
6
7 103 reproductive mode [22]. This allowed us to synthesise a wide range of ecological processes
8
9 104 driven by specialised plant-animal interactions and to explore potential outcomes of changing
10
11 105 fire regimes on these processes. We then reviewed traits involved in these specialist plant-
12
13 106 animal interactions to identify evidence of natural selection or evolution on ecological time
14
15 107 scales. This synthesis allowed us to draw some conclusions about how changes in fire
16
17 108 regimes might influence eco-evolutionary feedbacks in specialist plant-animal interactions.
18
19 109 This information will help us understand the dynamics of tightly coupled relationships that
20
21 110 are affected by fire, and will inform planning of appropriate management and conservation
22
23 111 interventions.

112

113 **Plant-animal interactions in fire-prone ecosystems**

114

115 We searched the literature to identify specialist interactions (i.e., a single genera dependent
116 on one to two genera in a single family of plant or animal for pollination, dispersal, food, or
117 habitat) where the interaction was mediated by fire. Given the specificity and infancy of this
118 research topic, our review was semi-systematic, combining formal literature searches with
119 information found through our general reading. Using Web of Science on the 15th of October
120 2023 and Scopus on the 26th of October 2023, we searched the literature using the following
121 terms: *ecolog**, *enviro**, *fire*, *specialist interaction*, *plant-animal interaction*, *plant*, *animal*,
122 *commensal*, *mutual* interaction*, and *antagonist* interaction*, *pollinat**, *herbiv**, *predat**, *eco-*
123 *evolution**, and *eco-evolutionary dynamics*. Results from Web of Science revealed that
124 specialist insect interactions beyond pollination were not being captured in these search
125 terms. We thus conducted a second search on both platforms for consistency across the
126 databases on the 26th of October 2023 using the search strings: ‘fire AND specialis* AND
127 insect’ and ‘fire AND specialist AND larva*’.

128

129 Our searches retrieved 358 papers from Web of Science and 212 papers from Scopus, with no
130 overlap between the databases. Titles and abstracts were screened using RevTools [58] in R
131 4.3.1 [59] to filter only empirical data papers which explicitly analysed the effects of fire and
132 specifically mentioned a plant-animal interaction. A study might have examined effects of
133 grazing and fire grouped as ‘disturbance’ but was only included in our review if fire effects

1
2
3 134 could be separated from other disturbances. Title screening resulted in 157 papers from Web
4
5 135 of Science and 47 papers from Scopus. Abstracts were then screened for the same criteria,
6
7 136 resulting in 62 papers from Web of Science and 16 from Scopus. Whole article screening was
8
9 137 then performed to ensure that the plant-animal interactions fit our definition of a specialised
10
11 138 interaction and the species involved in the interaction were named in the paper, giving a final
12
13 139 set of 25 papers.

14
15 140

16 141 Our review was complicated by the fact that plant-animal interactions or specialist
17
18 142 interactions are rarely framed as such in fire ecology literature. For example, the Australian
19
20 143 Mallee Emu-wren is dependent on grasses in the genus *Triodia* (Poaceae) and has been nearly
21
22 144 driven to extinction by changing fire regimes and habitat loss [60]. This is rarely described as
23
24 145 a specialist plant-animal interaction because *Triodia* is so widespread and commonly
25
26 146 described only in terms of being habitat for the bird [61]. Thus, we added 24 papers to the list
27
28 147 from the systematic search of which we were aware through our general reading (table S1).
29
30 148 Specialist plant-animal interactions were assessed on a case-basis, drawing upon multiple
31
32 149 papers where available, rather than on a publication basis (i.e., referring to only the most
33
34 150 recent study of the interaction). In order to identify how changing fire regimes might impact
35
36 151 these interactions, we classified key plant and animal traits that contributed to their
37
38 152 persistence and the strength of selection on these traits (figure 1).

39
40 153

41 154 Our aim was to understand how changing fire regimes would impact plant-animal
42
43 155 interactions but the fire ecology of species in each study was not always described and, in
44
45 156 many cases, might be unknown. Plants are the foundation of animal habitat and
46
47 157 understanding plant responses to fire was necessary to identify potential changes to plant-
48
49 158 animal interactions. Therefore, we conducted additional research on each case study to
50
51 159 classify the plant species in the interaction by its post-fire reproductive mode [22] – one of
52
53 160 the most important traits determining plant fire responses. For most cases, we retrieved this
54
55 161 information from the TRY plant database [62], AusTraits [63], BROT [64], or the Fire
56
57 162 Effects Information System [65] (table S1). For 14 plant species where post-fire reproductive
58
59 163 mode was unavailable in the databases, we used the scientific literature (table S1). On
60
61 164 conclusion of this research, the post-fire reproductive mode remained unknown for nine plant
62
63 165 species (table S1). This process provided baseline information to help make predictions about
64
65 166 the potential effects of changing fire regimes on the interactions identified in our review.

66
67 167

1
2
3 168 As mutualisms vary in their degree of dependency [66], we categorised mutualisms as
4
5 169 facultative or obligate. Obligate mutualisms are those where both interactors benefit from the
6
7 170 interaction and are solely dependent on each other for survival [66]. Facultative mutualisms
8
9 171 are those where both interactors benefit but there is no dependency of either interactor for
10
11 172 survival [66]. Given that our review focussed on specialised interactions, facultative
12
13 173 mutualisms were used to describe interactions where both interactors benefit, but only one
14
15 174 interactor is dependent on the other for survival. For facultative mutualisms to be considered
16
17 175 specialised, only one interactor need fit the definition of a specialist, while the other
18
19 176 interactor may be more generalist in nature (e.g., a pollinator specialised on a single host
20
21 177 plant family, while the host plant family is pollinated by other pollinator families). The same
22
23 178 conditions applied to commensal and antagonistic interactions where only one interactor was
24
25 179 considered specialist. Some species included in our review had undergone binomial
26
27 180 nomenclature revisions since publication, and we included the current name while listing the
28
29 181 basionym for the original publication in table S1.

182
29 183 Our review revealed 48 cases where fire influenced specialist plant-animal interactions (table
30
31 184 S1). These were mutualisms (17 cases) including pollination, dispersal, food and protection
32
33 185 provision; commensal interactions (8 cases) including habitat and protection provision; and
34
35 186 antagonistic interactions (11 cases) including seed predation, herbivory, and parasitism. We
36
37 187 also identified specialised multi-faceted interactions which occurred between more than two
38
39 188 interactors (16 cases). In our review, papers either studied the impacts of singular fire events
40
41 189 (e.g., a wildfire, prescribed fire, or experimental burn) or fire regimes (e.g., spatio-temporal
42
43 190 patterns of fire) on specialised plant-animal interactions. Papers in our review were published
44
45 191 between 1966-2021, however, most (n = 45) were published since 2004, with only a few
46
47 192 (n=4) published prior to 1999. Papers mainly reported data from North America and Central
48
49 193 America (n = 22) and Australia (n = 16), with a small number from Africa (n = 5), South
50
51 194 America (Brazil and Argentina, n = 3), Europe (Spain, n = 2), and Asia (South Korea, n = 1).

195

196 **Mutualistic interactions**

197

198 *Pollination*

199

200 We identified nine specialist pollinator interactions including weevils, moths, bees, and
201 wasps in fire-prone shrublands (table S1). In Mediterranean subtropical shrublands of Spain,

1
2
3 202 the dwarf palm *Chamaerops humilis* (Arecaceae) is primarily pollinated by the weevil
4 203 *Derelomus chamaeropsis* (Curculionidae) [35]. In return for pollination, *C. humilis* provides
5 204 *D. chamaeropsis* with food and habitat in the form of egg-deposition and larval development
6 205 sites in persistent old inflorescences (figure 1) [35, 67]. Larval development exerts a fitness
7 206 cost on the palm by limiting reproductive success, thus, *C. humilis* prevents larval
8 207 development during fruit development in female inflorescences (figure 1) [68]. Odour
9 208 mimicry and flowering synchronicity attracts weevils to male and female *C. humilis*, despite
10 209 the lower pollination reward from females (figure 1) [35, 69]. Following fire, *C. humilis*
11 210 resprouts, grows rapidly and resumes flower production the following spring [35, 70].
12 211 However, *D. chamaeropsis* is often less abundant in the immediate post-fire environment due
13 212 to fire-related mortality, with recovery reliant on recolonisation of burnt sites [35]. In this
14 213 post-fire stage, *C. humilis* is also pollinated, albeit to a lesser degree by the sap beetle
15 214 *Meligethinus pallidulus* (Nitidulidae), protected from fire in stems of *C. humilis* and
16 215 temporarily replacing the weevil as the primary pollinator [35]. Selection pressure from the
17 216 weevil affects seed production in *C. humilis* through traits such as flowering synchronicity
18 217 which likely feeds back into weevil population dynamics (figure 1). This example shows how
19 218 co-evolution in a plant-animal interaction is maintained by fire.

20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34 220 Two studies in desert shrublands of North America examined how wildfire influenced
35 221 interactions between *Yucca* moths in the genera *Tegeticula* and *Parategeticula* (Proxidae)
36 222 which specialise on pollinating *Yucca spp.* (Asparagaceae) [71, 72]. Obligate nursery
37 223 pollination mutualisms occur between *Yucca brevifolia* and *Tegeticula synthetica* and *T.*
38 224 *antithetica* [73, 74], and between *Y. baccata* and *T. yuccasella*, with larvae consuming only a
39 225 fraction of the seeds [73, 75]. Agavaceae are known to selectively abscise flowers in response
40 226 to small pollen loads or self-pollination [75]. Therefore, reinforcing selection for high
41 227 pollination efficiency but relatively lower egg deposition in *Yucca* moths has been suggested
42 228 to reduce the risk of flower mortality prior to larval development (figure 1) [75]. High
43 229 pollination efficiency in *Yucca* moths increases *Yucca spp.* fitness, and has led to
44 230 disinvestment in an ancestral co-pollinator due to the higher energetic cost to sustain its
45 231 mutualism [75]. Adult *Y. brevifolia* and *Y. baccata* are killed by fire but have post-fire
46 232 resprouting capabilities (table S1). However, their post-fire recovery is limited by the low
47 233 desert precipitation (figure 1) [76, 77]. This means that both *Yucca* moth larvae and their host
48 234 plants are vulnerable to fire-induced mortality while adult moths may survive fire through
49 235 underground nesting (figure 1) [72]. However, low dispersal ability of adults (e.g., ca. 8 m

1
2
3 236 dispersal for pollen transfer) [72] coupled with limited post-fire recruitment of *Yucca spp.*,
4 237 could result in local extirpation of *Yucca* moths where frequent fire and drought limit *Yucca*
5 238 *spp.* recruitment (figure 1).
6
7
8
9

239

10 240 In the same North American desert, the shrub *Krameria grayi* (Krameriaceae) provides oil to
11 241 bees in the genus *Centris* (subgenera *Paracentris*, Apidae) for larval provisioning and nest
12 242 building (table S1) [72, 78, 79]. This is a facultative mutualism, with *K. grayi* reliant on
13 243 *Centris* bees, while the bees are able to collect oil from other plant families [78]. *Krameria*
14 244 *grayi* aboveground biomass is killed by fire [72] and resprouts from the root following fire
15 245 (table S1) [80]. Low post-fire resprouting in *K. grayi* may be attributed to mortality and
16 246 growth restrictions due to water stress in desert ecosystems or increased root growth at the
17 247 expense of above ground growth (figure 1) [81, 82]. Although adult *Paracentris* bees survive
18 248 fire by nesting underground [72], limited regeneration of their host species, *K. grayi*, means
19 249 that very intense or frequent fires could lead to a local collapse in the bee population where
20 250 *K. grayi* is the dominant host species (figure 1). Over evolutionary time, oil production in
21 251 plants has been lost multiple times and, in some cases, was driven by the loss of pollinators
22 252 [83]. Co-evolution between oil bees and oil flowers has produced specialised morphologies
23 253 and oil bee behaviours which assist oil collection [84, 85]. Thus, selection for oil production
24 254 in *K. grayi* is likely to be driven by the beneficial effect of the oil on the bee populations [79,
25 255 84] (figure 1).
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38

256

39 257 In North American temperate sagebrush steppe, *Diadasia enavata* (Apidae) and *Megachile*
40 258 *parallela* (Megachilidae) are two oligolectic bee species (i.e., bees with narrow diet
41 259 specialisation) that pollinate wild sunflower, *Helianthus annuus* (Asteraceae) (table S1) [86].
42 260 These are facultative mutualisms, with *D. enavata* and *M. parallela* reliant on *H. annuus*
43 261 while the sunflowers are also pollinated by generalist honeybees, *Apis mellifera*, and bumble
44 262 bees, *Bombus terrestris* (Apidae) [87, 88]. *Diadasia enavata* and *M. parallela* bees nest
45 263 underground [86] which likely results in their protection during fire (figure 1). However, both
46 264 bee species were found to be highly sensitive to a large wildfire which razed 121, 400 ha of
47 265 sagebrush steppe in 2010, leaving only small strips of *H. annuus* remaining along roadsides
48 266 [86]. *Helianthus annuus* does not resprout (table S1) [62], and post-fire recovery is likely
49 267 reliant on seed dispersal to the burnt area. These bee species are restricted to patches of
50 268 unburnt habitat during vegetation recovery, leaving them at risk of predation during foraging
51 269 [86]. Oligolectic bees are also limited in exploiting new hosts as they rely on floral scent
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 270 recognition and have lower larval fitness when feeding on pollen of other hosts [89, 90]. If
4
5 271 sunflowers were unable to recover following severe wildfire, local extinction of the bees
6
7 272 could follow, as partner switching is unlikely in *Diadasia* bees [91, 92]. Sensitivity to large,
8
9 273 intense wildfires appears common in specialist pollinator species as their food sources are
10
11 274 restricted, resulting in longer post-fire recovery of the interaction [1].
12

12 275

13 276 Another hymenopteran pollinator in the same temperate sagebrush steppe is the wasp
14
15 277 *Pseudomasaris vespoides* (Vespidae) whose larvae feed on pollen of the forbs, *Penstemon*
16
17 278 *spp.* (Plantaginaceae) (table S1) [93]. This is a facultative mutualism, whereby *P. vespoides*
18
19 279 relies on *Penstemon* species for food, while *Penstemon* can be pollinated by other insects or
20
21 280 hummingbirds [94]. Both *P. vespoides* and *P. cyaneus* are sensitive to fire as the wasp
22
23 281 produces nests on rocks and woody stems exposing them to excessive heat during fire [93].
24
25 282 *Penstemon cyaneus* is killed by high intensity fire as the basal buds which often confer
26
27 283 resprouting capacity, are located on the rosette surface, rather than underground (table S1)
28
29 284 [93]. Thus, fire intensity would act as a limiting factor for *P. vespoides* nest survival and
30
31 285 post-fire resprouting in *P. cyaneus*. If *P. vespoides* pollination was restricted by increasing
32
33 286 fire frequency and/or intensity, *Penstemon spp.* could potentially switch to a hummingbird
34
35 287 pollination syndrome [94]. Hummingbirds have traits allowing them to recolonise burnt areas
36
37 288 and exploit post fire-flowering [95]. This type of wasp-to-hummingbird pollination transition
38
39 289 has occurred numerous times in *Penstemon*, but backwards transitions (hummingbird-to-
40
41 290 wasp) have not been recorded [94]. In this ecosystem, more frequent or intense fires could
42
43 291 result in local population declines for both species or potential collapse of the interaction,
44
45 292 with the wasps being most at risk due to their specificity.
46

43 293

44 294 Contrary to these fire-sensitive mutualisms, another bee-plant mutualism in the same
45
46 295 ecosystem was not harmed by fire [93]. *Micrandrena* (subgenera of *Andrena*, Andrenidae)
47
48 296 oligolectic bees pollinate forbs of *Lomatium spp.*, including *Lomatium dissectum* (Apiaceae)
49
50 297 (table S1) [93]. This is a facultative mutualism with *Micrandrena* bees reliant on *Lomatium*
51
52 298 *spp.* for pollen, while *L. dissectum* is able to self-pollinate, or be pollinated by other bee
53
54 299 species in the Apidae and Halictidae families, albeit with fewer visitors [96, 97]. Fire
55
56 300 seasonality appears to be important to this interaction because pollination and seed
57
58 301 production occur before the fire season [98, 99]. However, this interaction appears to involve
59
60 302 traits that confer resistance to changes in fire regimes. For example, despite resprouting
303
304 303 ability, *L. dissectum* also produces dormant seeds which could sustain the mutualism even

1
2
3 304 under more frequent fires (figure 1) [98]. Furthermore, *Micrandrena* bees nest underground
4
5 305 lowering their susceptibility to mortality during fire (figure 1) [93].
6
7 306

8 307 *Dispersal and food provision*
9

10 308
11
12 309 We identified a single fire-dependent specialist dispersal and food provisioning interaction
13
14 310 from fire-prone shrublands (fynbos) and grasslands of the southwestern Cape, South Africa,
15
16 311 where fire-sensitive forests occur among rocky outcrops (table S1) [100]. Fleshy fruit of the
17
18 312 Rockwood tree, *Heeria argentea* (Anacardiaceae) are dispersed by the generalist frugivore
19
20 313 Namaqua rock rat, *Aethomys namaquensis* (Muridae), which moves *H. argentea* seeds within
21
22 314 and between rocky outcrops [100]. This is a specialised facultative mutualism as *H. argentea*
23
24 315 is reliant on the rat, not only for dispersal to low fire frequency areas, but also for breaking
25
26 316 seed dormancy and triggering germination which otherwise fails without pericarp
27
28 317 consumption [100]. The fleshy fruits of *H. argentea* makes them sensitive to fire [101], and
29
30 318 aboveground biomass of the plants are killed by fire with no fire-stimulated germination or
31
32 319 resprouting (table S1) [100]. The rat consumes only the pericarp of the seed, so seeds are
33
34 320 adequately dispersed while the rat receives a food source [100]. Thus, strong selection on
35
36 321 seed pericarp production and seed dormancy in *H. argentea* promotes dispersal by *A.*
37
38 322 *namaquensis* and allows this fire-sensitive forest tree to remain connected across fire-free
39
40 323 refugia, within a broader landscape maintained by recurrent fire (figure 1).
41
42 324

43 325 *Food, habitat, and protection provision*
44

45 326
46
47 327 We identified eight mutualistic food and protection provision interactions, in the Americas
48
49 328 and Africa (table S1) [102-107]. In South American tropical savanna, a mutualistic
50
51 329 interaction occurs between the bromeliad, *Bromelia balansae* (Bromeliaceae), and the spider,
52
53 330 *Psecas chapoda* (Salticidae), a predatory carnivore (table S1) [102, 108]. Fires are frequent in
54
55 331 this system, with plant species typically adapted to fires of a range of intensities (e.g., 500 to
56
57 332 50,000 kw/m [109]). *Bromelia balansae* can resprout post-fire (table S1) [110] and its
58
59 333 rosettes act as a foraging, reproductive, and nursery site for the spiders [102, 108]. Spider
60
334 faeces and their prey carcasses are absorbed by bromeliad trichomes, providing nutrients to
335 the plant, and spiders deter herbivores [102, 108]. This is a facultative mutualism as *P.*
336 *chapoda* relies on bromeliaceous species, including *Bromelia balansae*, *Ananas comosus*, and
337 *Aechmea distichantha* (Bromeliaceae), for their entire life cycle [102, 108, 111]. *Bromelia*

1
2
3 338 *balansae* can gain nutrients in the absence of the spider, but its growth is greater in the
4
5 339 presence of the spiders [108], likely increasing *B. balansae* survival through recurrent fires.
6
7 340 Other Bromeliaceae species, and their associated animals, have shown high mortality
8
9 341 following high intensity wildfires despite the bromeliads resprouting capacity [112, 113].
10
11 342 Therefore, fire intensity is a key environmental parameter influencing the outcome of food
12
13 343 provision and shelter interactions (figure 1), with changes in fire intensity disrupting these
14
15 344 mutualisms [102].

345

16
17 346 We identified a number of mutualistic food and protection interactions in Central America,
18
19 347 Mexico and Africa between thorn trees (*Vachellia spp.*, Fabaceae) and ants of Formicidae
20
21 348 (table S1) [103-106, 114, 115]. *Vachellia spp.* produce swollen thorns, extrafloral nectaries,
22
23 349 and modified leaflet tips which provide food, habitat, and protection from fire for ant
24
25 350 populations as the thorns do not readily ignite [103, 104, 114]. These are obligate mutualisms
26
27 351 as ants protect the plants from herbivores by attacking them [114]. Ants also protect the
28
29 352 plants from fire as their behaviour creates a cleared area around the tree base, reducing fuel
30
31 353 load [103-106, 114, 115]. Ants only consume the leaflet tips and collect nectar from
32
33 354 extrafloral nectaries, which limits overgrazing [103]. In the absence of ants, the plants can
34
35 355 lose competitive ability against other plant species and suffer severe defoliation from
36
37 356 herbivory with increased mortality, especially post-fire [103, 104, 106, 114, 115]. *Vachellia*
38
39 357 *spp.* require intermediate fire frequencies for population turnover and regeneration with rapid
40
41 358 post-fire resprouting and development of thorns, nectaries, and leaflet tips which maintain the
42
43 359 mutualistic associations with ant colonies (table S1) [103, 106, 114]. Production of extrafloral
44
45 360 nectaries has been associated with a disinvestment in defence chemical production [114,
46
47 361 116]. *Vachellia spp.* are completely reliant on the ants for protection, meaning extrafloral
48
49 362 nectary and swollen thorn production are both under strong selection pressure and high
50
51 363 intensity fire could disrupt this mutualism [103].

364

365 **Commensal interactions**

366

367 *Habitat or protection provision*

368

56
57 369 We identified eight animal species having a commensal habitat association with spinifex
58
59 370 grasses in the genus *Triodia* (Poaceae) in Australia (table S1). Many Australian passerines are
60
371 habitat specialists relying on spinifex grasslands for nesting and protection from predators

1
2
3 372 (table S1), including (but not limited to) *Amytornis dorotheae* in tropical savanna, *Amytornis*
4 373 *woodwardi* in tropical plateau spinifex, and *Stipiturus mallee* (Maluridae) in semi-arid mallee
5 374 shrubland [117-124]. *Triodia* species have both seeding and resprouting post-fire
6 375 reproductive modes (table S1), but *Triodia* takes a long time to develop high density tussocks
7 376 (e.g., 15-30 years post-fire) because of their sclerophyllous leaves and low precipitation in
8 377 their arid and semi-arid habitat [125-128]. This means that *Triodia*-specialist birds are
9 378 typically absent from habitat burnt within 15 years [120, 121]. Variability in post-fire
10 379 successional stages, coupled with limited dispersal, causes *A. dorotheae* and *S. mallee* to
11 380 form distinct metapopulations in otherwise continuous habitat but also puts them at greater
12 381 risk of mortality from intense fires [117-123]. Local extinctions [123] and failed
13 382 translocations [129] in *S. mallee* have been driven by fire regimes which shift the ecosystems
14 383 into a state dominated by early and mid-successional vegetation, a process affecting a range
15 384 of other species [130].

16 385
17 386 *Triodia* grasslands cover almost 30% of the Australian continent [61], resulting in many
18 387 Australian lizards also relying on *Triodia*, including (but not limited to) those in the genera
19 388 *Ctenotus* (Scincidae), *Ctenophorus* (Agamidae), and *Delma* (Pygopodidae) (table S1) [131-
20 389 133]. This widespread distribution has long been thought to be a driver of Australia's high
21 390 reptile diversity, as it provides shelter and food to the lizards in the form of termites which
22 391 are the main consumers of *Triodia* [134, 135]. Some *Triodia*-dependent lizards decline
23 392 immediately post-fire and take at least five years, and often many more, to recover or reach
24 393 their peak abundance [131-133]. The small marsupial carnivore Southern Ningui, *Ningui*
25 394 *yvonneae* (Dasyuridae), is another mid- to late successional *Triodia* specialist from semi-arid
26 395 mallee shrublands [130, 136, 137]. *Ningui yvonneae* uses *Triodia* hummocks and ground
27 396 litter as foraging grounds for invertebrate and vertebrate prey [130, 136] and is completely
28 397 absent from areas burnt within five years [131]. Like the grasswrens, *Triodia*-specialist
29 398 reptiles and mammals are sensitive to fire regimes which shift the ecosystem into an early or
30 399 mid-successional state [130, 137].

31 400
32 401 Given the commensal nature of these relationships, it is unlikely that these *Triodia*-specialist
33 402 animals pose a strong selection pressure on *Triodia spp.*. However, fire return interval is a
34 403 critical parameter influencing the distribution and abundance of *Triodia* grasses [125] (figure
35 404 1), which directly relates to the recovery and persistence of these *Triodia* specialist animals.
36 405

1
2
3 406 **Antagonistic interactions**
4

5 407

6 408 *Seed predation*
7

8 409
9

10 410 We identified five specialist antagonistic seed predation interactions in shrublands of
11 411 Argentina and Spain, and in North American and Australian forests. These specialist seed
12 412 predators in Argentina and Spain are phytophagous (i.e., plant feeding) insects which spend
13 413 their entire life cycles on a single host plant (table S1) [138, 139]. Seeds from the climbing
14 414 plant *Rhynchosia edulis* (Fabaceae) and Mediterranean gorse *Ulex parviflorus* (Fabaceae) are
15 415 consumed by the weevils *Acanthoscelides spp.* (Chrysomelidae) and *Exapion fasciolatum*
16 416 (Apionidae), respectively (table S1) [138, 139]. In both cases, phytophagous insect eggs are
17 417 deposited in flower ovaries and larvae feed on the seed [138, 139]. Seeds from the herb,
18 418 *Asphodelus ramosus* (Asphodelaceae), are similarly consumed by the bug *Horistus orientalis*
19 419 (Miridae), but eggs are deposited inside the inflorescence stalk, with larvae and adults
20 420 feeding on the leaves, flowers, fruits and seeds (table S1) [139]. In all these cases, fire
21 421 disrupts the antagonistic interaction by temporarily reducing host plant abundances and seed
22 422 predators [139]. Plant species respond to fire by triggering post-fire resprouting in *R. edulis*
23 423 [138], breaking seed dormancy and stimulating germination in *U. parviflorus* [139], and
24 424 triggering flowering in *A. ramosus* which is otherwise limited in high density unburnt
25 425 shrubland (table S1) [139]. Although obligate seeding species, such as *U. parviflorus* (table
26 426 S1), face immaturity risk under very frequent fire (e.g., every 2 years) they are also limited
27 427 under fire exclusion which reduces opportunities for post-fire seed regeneration [139-141].
28 428 Thus, short fire return intervals (e.g., every 5 years) would generally favour the plant species
29 429 of these specialised antagonistic interactions, provided they are longer than the time to
30 430 maturity (figure 1).
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47

48 431

49 432 In western North American coniferous forests, the American red squirrel, *Tamiasciurus*
50 433 *hudsonicus* (Sciuridae), is a seed predator of the dominant tree species Rocky Mountain
51 434 lodgepole pine, *Pinus contorta latifolia* (Pinaceae) [55, 56]. Fires in this ecosystem occur
52 435 every 75-300 years and fire prevents successional progression to spruce-fir climax
53 436 communities which have lower fire frequencies [142, 143]. *Pinus contorta latifolia* is an
54 437 obligate seeder, which releases seed from serotinous cones following fire, resulting in mass
55 438 recruitment events that produce dense, even-aged stands [62, 143-145]. However, *P. contorta*
56 439 *latifolia* requires ca. 70 years to develop a substantial seed bank placing this tree species

1
2
3 440 under immaturity risk if fires occur more frequently than its time to maturity [146, 147].
4
5 441 Increasing fire frequencies also place selection pressure on serotiny, a heritable trait where
6
7 442 cones remain closed until an environmental trigger causes them to open, as it confers seed
8
9 443 survival during fire (figure 1) [55, 56]. However, this trait is also under strong negative
10
11 444 selection pressure from pre-dispersal seed predation by *T. hudsonicus* due to their selective
12
13 445 harvesting of serotinous cones (figure 1) [55, 56]. Any change in fire frequency can cause
14
15 446 shifts in the vegetation community with projections showing transitions from forests to
16
17 447 shrublands under increasing fire frequency [142, 148] lowering food resources and the dense
18
19 448 canopies characteristic of *T. hudsonicus* habitat [149]. Conversely, a decrease in fire
20
21 449 frequency allowing the spruce-fire climax community [142, 148] would also decrease food
22
23 450 resource availability for *T. hudsonicus* due to low *P. contorta latifolia* population turnover as
24
25 451 stands senesce [147]. This interaction results in spatial variation in serotiny, demonstrating
26
27 452 how fire influences plant and animal traits under selection, which can subsequently feed back
28
29 453 into population processes.

30
31 454
32 455 Another specialist seed predator is the Glossy black-cockatoo, *Calyptorhynchus lathami*
33
34 456 (Cacatuidae) [150, 151], which feed solely on the seeds from 12 serotinous tree species in the
35
36 457 Casuarinaceae family (she-oaks) in woodlands and forests of eastern Australia [152, 153]
37
38 458 [154]. While two Glossy black-cockatoo subspecies exist, the plant-animal interaction
39
40 459 involving *C. lathami halmaturinus* was, to our knowledge, the only subspecies studied in
41
42 460 relation to fire. On Kangaroo Island, South Australia, *C. lathami halmaturinus* feeds
43
44 461 exclusively on *Allocasuarina verticillata* [153]. Very little is known about the effect of *C.*
45
46 462 *lathami* predation on she-oaks themselves, but seed predation by cockatoos exerts strong
47
48 463 selection pressure on other Australian serotinous species [155, 156]. *Allocasuarina*
49
50 464 *verticillata* is a facultative resprouter (table S1) [153, 157] but has poor resprouting and seed
51
52 465 regeneration in the absence of fire [153]. In *A. verticillata*, fruits appear at 5-10 years of age,
53
54 466 but seedbanks take 20 years to accumulate adequately for recruitment [153], meaning
55
56 467 frequent fire (e.g., every 5-10 years) limits she-oak recovery. The cockatoos display variable
57
58 468 geographical selection of seed, due to tight energy budgets, avoiding recently burnt (e.g., <10
59
60 469 years post-fire) and long unburnt stands (e.g., >60 years post-fire) due to low cone abundance
470 or low cone quality, respectively [153, 154]. Thus, fire frequency is a critical factor in
471 maintaining food sources for the Glossy black-cockatoo (figure 1). *Calyptorhynchus lathami*
472 *halmaturinus* is currently limited to Kangaroo Island, where increases in large high intensity
473 and frequent wildfires have limited food availability in an already limited foraging habitat

1
2
3 474 [153]. High intensity fires have caused regional population declines in *C. lathami*
4
5 475 *halmaturinus*, highlighting the importance of maintaining unburned regions for persistence in
6
7 476 this specialised seed predator [153]. At the other extreme, if fire is excluded from an
8
9 477 ecosystem for more than 60 years, reductions in recruitment and canopy seedbank abundance
10
11 478 could lower food resource availability for *C. lathami* [153, 154].

12 479

13
14 480 Fire controls plant abundances and, thus, food resources essential to these specialist
15
16 481 antagonistic seed predators (figure 1). Single fire events can temporarily reduce host plant
17
18 482 abundances and, thus, seed predation, allowing for plant recruitment processes under lower
19
20 483 biotic pressures. Partner switching, whereby an animal species switches its primary food
21
22 484 source plant, has been documented in response to food resource fluctuations in non-fire
23
24 485 research [158, 159]. Whether a species such as *C. lathami* could switch permanently to
25
26 486 alternative food sources is unknown, but this species has been observed to feed on other
27
28 487 species in response to temporary food shortages [154, 160]. If partner switching did not
29
30 488 occur, an abrupt fire regime change is more likely to cause subsequent collapses in such
31
32 489 antagonistic plant-animal interactions.

33 490

34 491 *Herbivory*

35 492

36 493 We identified six specialist antagonistic herbivore interactions involving larval butterflies and
37
38 494 adult beetles and bugs (table S1). Adult butterflies of specialist larval butterflies identified in
39
40 495 these cases are generalist pollinators [161-163]. Therefore, these interactions were considered
41
42 496 antagonistic only at the larval stage as larval herbivory results in stem defoliation which
43
44 497 limits plant growth [164, 165]. In North American temperate shrublands, grasslands and
45
46 498 forests, perennial forbs in the *Viola* genera (Violaceae), including *Viola pedata*, *V. pedatifida*,
47
48 499 *V. sororia*, *V. sagittata*, and *V. bicolor* are larval hostplants for *Speyeria idalia* and *S. cybele*
49
50 500 (Nymphalidae) (table S1) [164, 166-174]. *Viola sororia* is the only known resprouter of these
51
52 501 *Viola* species (table S1) but other *Viola* species are known to resprout [63], and some increase
53
54 502 in abundance with increasing fire frequency [168]. Butterfly larvae of *Cercyonis pegala*
55
56 503 (Nymphalidae) specialise on *Tridens flavus* (Poaceae), a post-fire resprouter, in North
57
58 504 American temperate prairie (table S1) [166, 169, 170]. *Polygona c-aureum* (Nymphalidae) is
59
60 505 another larval specialist butterfly found in subtropical forests and grasslands of South Korea
60 506 [175]. Larvae of this species feed on the vines *Humulus japonicus* and *H. lupulus*
60 507 (Cannabaceae) which have increased growth post-fire due to gap creation [175] (table S1).

1
2
3 508 Resprouting is important for these host plants, conferring plant re-establishment, and for the
4 509 persistence of butterfly populations by increasing nectar source abundance and egg
5 510 deposition substrate for adults (figure 1) [166, 173, 176]. More frequent fire might lead to
6 511 higher rates of herbivory by reducing habitat complexity, promoting butterfly larvae ability to
7 512 locate host plants [177].
8
9

10 513
11
12 514 We identified one coleopteran and one hemipteran species as specialist herbivores in fire
13 515 maintained North American ecosystems. In temperate sagebrush steppe, the beetle, *Trirhabda*
14 516 *lewisii* (Chrysomelidae) feeds on the foliage of the shrub *Ericameria nauseosa* (Asteraceae)
15 517 and can completely defoliate the shrubs, sometimes causing plant death (table S1) [178]. In
16 518 temperate oak savanna, the oak lace bug, *Corythucha arcuata* (Tingidae) is entirely reliant on
17 519 the oak tree, *Quercus macrocarpa* (Fagaceae), for their life cycle, feeding on leaf mesophyll
18 520 (table S1) [179, 180]. Feeding by *C. arcuata* results in leaf discolouration [179] reducing the
19 521 oak's photosynthetic capacity [181]. In both cases, the plant species can resprout post-fire
20 522 (table S1) with fires temporarily disrupting these antagonistic herbivorous interactions due to
21 523 insect mortality [178, 179, 182, 183]. However, fire can produce more appealing plant
22 524 material for *T. lewisii*, resulting in increased herbivory and, therefore, post-fire mortality in *E.*
23 525 *nauseosa* [178]. *Quercus macrocarpa* usually survives low intensity fires by resprouting,
24 526 with canopy gaps produced by fire increasing their growth but also leaf quality for *C. arcuata*
25 527 [179, 183]. Consequently, fires can result in higher densities of both of these specialist
26 528 herbivores due to higher quality plant material [178, 179]. Frequent but low intensity patchy
27 529 fires, which do not compromise the plant's capacity to reach maturity (figure 1), can maintain
28 530 high quality food resources for specialist herbivores by triggering regeneration of their food
29 531 plants. Outside of this North American system, *C. arcuata* can feed on other plant families
30 532 [180] suggesting an ability to shift host plants if fire regimes became unfavourable (e.g.,
31 533 increases in fire frequency). If plant hosts were released from their enemies, resource
32 534 allocation could shift from plant defence to other population processes such as individual
33 535 growth [184].
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 537 **Multi-faceted interactions**
4

5 538

6 539 *Food and protection interactions*
7

8 540
9

10 541 We identified two multi-faceted food and protection interactions between butterfly species,
11 542 their larval host plant, and ant species (table S1). In North American temperate upland
12 543 prairie, *Icaricia icarioides fenderi* (Lycaenidae) larvae feed on the leguminous lupines,
13 544 *Lupinus sulphureus*, *L. sulphureus kincaidii*, *L. argenteus laxiflorus*, and *L. arbustus*
14 545 (Fabaceae), which also act as a nectar source for adult butterflies (table S1) [185-187]. The
15 546 association with *Lupinus spp.* was considered specialised only at the larval stage as adult
16 547 butterflies collect nectar from other plant families [188] and these *Lupinus spp.* are also
17 548 pollinated by bees and flies [189]. Associations between *Lupinus spp.* and *I. icarioides*
18 549 *fenderi* larvae are antagonistic as the larvae feed on young leaves and apical meristems [186,
19 550 190], reducing plant growth. *Icaricia icarioides fenderi* also have a facultative mutualistic
20 551 association with ants (Formicidae) as their myrmecophilous organs provide nutrients to the
21 552 ants, while the ants protect the butterfly larvae from predation and parasitism [185]. In this
22 553 case, the effect of fire on the ants was not directly investigated, but the ants likely seek refuge
23 554 from fire in underground nests, conferring survival [104]. While the ant-butterfly larvae
24 555 association in these species is only facultative, this mutualism allows butterfly larvae to
25 556 inhabit enemy-free space [191]. The butterfly larvae are killed by fire [185, 187] but adult
26 557 butterflies quickly recolonise burnt areas and increase their reproduction in the year after fire
27 558 [186] suggesting resilience of *I. icarioides fenderi* to certain fire regimes. *Lupinus sulphureus*
28 559 is a resprouter, and both post-fire resprouting and seeding has been recorded in *Lupinus*
29 560 species (table S1) [192, 193]. Thus, *Lupinus spp.* on which *I. icarioides fenderi* relies are
30 561 likely to resprout, allowing fast re-establishment of these interactions. Favourable fire
31 562 regimes (e.g., burning a proportion of the habitat each year) are essential for maintaining a
32 563 mosaic of regenerating burnt and unburnt habitat for the persistence of this specialised
33 564 interaction (figure 1) [186, 187].
34
35

36 565

37 566 In Mexican subtropical forests the shrub, *Croton repens* (Euphorbiaceae), butterfly, *Anatole*
38 567 *rossi* (Riodinidae) and ant, *Camponotus atriceps* (Formicidae) form specialised interactions
39 568 (table S1) [194]. Adult butterflies almost exclusively rely on *Croton repens* for nectar but
40 569 have been observed feeding on *Ruellia spp.* (Acanthaceae) and *Calea longipedicellata*
41 570 (Asteraceae) [194]. It is unknown if other species may act as pollinators for *C. repens*, but

1
2
3 571 other *Croton* species have generalist wasp and bee pollinators [195]. *Anatole rossi* larvae
4 572 completely defoliate *C. repens* and feed on new buds, limiting growth [194], indicating an
5 573 antagonistic interaction. However, these shrubs can produce new growth quickly in the
6 574 absence of *A. rossi* larvae [194]. *Anatole rossi* larvae possess myrmecophilous organs which
7 575 promote ant tending through a facultative mutualism, as ants also collect honeydew from
8 576 other plants, but tending by *C. atriceps* is essential for *A. rossi* larvae survival [194].
9 577 Production of nectar and myrmecophilous organs is energetically costly for *A. rossi* larvae
10 578 [191], and the association with ants for larval survival likely drives selection on these traits
11 579 (figure 1). *Anatole rossi* larvae are protected from predation and fire as ants coerce them into
12 580 underground tunnels along tap roots of *C. repens* [194]. Fire is required for *C. repens* and the
13 581 maintenance of the interaction as fire triggers resprouting, reduces competition, and provides
14 582 egg deposition sites for female butterflies [194]. However, if fires becomes more intense and
15 583 severe, the underground tunnels might be too shallow to protect *A. rossi* larvae and ants,
16 584 resulting in mortality (figure 1) [194].
17 585

28 586 *Antagonistic parasitism – mutualistic dispersal and food interactions*

29 587
30 588 We identified 14 multi-faceted antagonistic parasitism – mutualistic dispersal and food
31 589 interactions, namely interactions occurring between host-specific mistletoes (Loranthaceae),
32 590 their hostplant, and avian vectors occurring in Brazil and Australia (table S1) [196-198].
33 591 Mistletoes are host-specific hemi-parasites (Santalales) which attach to hosts via a modified
34 592 root (i.e., haustorium) and can negatively impact their host by limiting water and nutrient
35 593 uptake [199]. Mistletoes are reliant on numerous bird species for dispersal [196, 197, 200],
36 594 but in Australia the mistletoe bird, *Dicaeum hirundinaceum* (Dicaeidae), is the most effective
37 595 disperser. The impacts of fire on mistletoe-dispersing birds will, therefore, have flow-on
38 596 effects for the parasite-host interaction [197]. Many mistletoe species occur in fire-prone
39 597 environments and most of their hosts plants have the capacity to resprout post-fire, and some
40 598 also have capacity for post-fire seeding (table S1) [62, 63, 197]. This facilitates quick re-
41 599 establishment of host plants following fire and likely also mistletoe parasitism. However,
42 600 three mistletoe host plants do not resprout (e.g., *Acacia monticola*, *Acacia xiphophylla*, and
43 601 *Vatairea macrocarpa* (Fabaceae)) and few mistletoe host plants are capable of post-fire
44 602 seeding (e.g., *Acacia aneura*, *Acacia monticola*, *Acacia xiphophylla*, *Lysiphyllum*
45 603 *cunninghamii* (Fabaceae), and *Grevillea wickhamii* (Proteaceae)), leaving these mistletoes
46 604 more susceptible to increasing fire frequencies and intensities (table S1) [201]. Mistletoes

1
2
3 605 generally lack the ability to resprout and would need to recolonise burnt areas through seed
4 606 dispersal (table S1) [196-198]. One mistletoe species in Australia, *Amyema sanguinea*
5 607 *sanguinea* (Loranthaceae), is able to resprout from the haustorium but only when of a
6 608 sufficient size to have thick bark providing protection from fire [197, 198]. Thus, mistletoe
7 609 size is an important characteristic related to the persistence of the parasitic interaction
8 610 through fire [196]. Fire seasonality is also important, as fires prior to flowering or seed
9 611 dispersal can inhibit reproduction in mistletoes, while fire prior to the wet season allows
10 612 hosts, and their parasites, to recover quickly [196]. In some cases, fire can increase mistletoe
11 613 recruitment by reducing vegetation density and increasing light availability for germination
12 614 and development [196-198]. However, fires that are too frequent (e.g., every 2 years) or
13 615 intense are likely to cause local population declines as mistletoe could be killed before seed
14 616 dispersal by mistletoe dispersing birds [196-198].

15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26 618 The mistletoe bird, *Dicaeum hirundinaceum*, has an alimentary canal adapted specifically for
27 619 a diet based on mistletoe fruits and defecation behaviour which ensures mistletoe seeds
28 620 adhere to host plant branches [197]. The interaction between *D. hirundinaceum* and mistletoe
29 621 is a specialised facultative mutualism in Australia as mistletoe berries comprise the majority
30 622 of their diet [202] but mistletoes are dispersed by other bird species [196, 197, 200].
31 623 Immediate post-fire dispersal of mistletoes seeds in Australia might also rely on more
32 624 generalist avian vectors (e.g., *Acanthagenys rufogularis*, *Canopophila whitei*, *Meliphaga*
33 625 *lewinii* (Meliphagidae) [197], and *Zosterops lateralis* (Zosteropidae) [200]), as a lack of
34 626 mistletoe food sources results in post-fire declines of *D. hirundinaceum* [203]. However,
35 627 mistletoe recruitment may decline if fires are frequent (e.g., every 2 years), as other avian
36 628 vectors may not disperse mistletoe at high rates and lack the specialised physiology and
37 629 defecation behaviour of *D. hirundinaceum* [203]. Thus, complex interactions occur between
38 630 mistletoes and fire, with fire regimes of low intensity and frequency (e.g., return interval >2
39 631 years) likely to promote mistletoe abundance, confer survival of their host plants, and allow
40 632 dispersal by avian vectors including the specialist *D. hirundinaceum* (figure 1).

41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

634 **Eco-evolutionary dynamics in fire-dependent interactions**

635

636 Eco-evolutionary feedbacks occur when ecological processes (e.g., demographic change and
637 species interactions) influence evolutionary changes (e.g., trait and allele frequencies),

1
2
3 638 subsequently feeding back into the ecological process (and vice versa) [204, 205]. A number
4
5 639 of criteria must be met for eco-evolutionary dynamics to be demonstrated. First, natural
6
7 640 selection or evolution must be shown to occur on ecological timescales (tens of generations
8
9 641 or fewer) [206, 207]. Second, the evolutionary change must feed back into the ecological
10
11 642 change via its influence on the environment, or the population dynamics of the plant or
12
13 643 animal involved in the interaction [206, 208]. Stabilising (negative) eco-evolutionary
14
15 644 feedbacks occur when directional changes in ecological or evolutionary processes trigger a
16
17 645 response from a species or environment which forces a negative response and subsequently
18
19 646 maintains the ecosystem at a stable state [209, 210]. Fire regimes which occur within the
20
21 647 range of variability under which the plant-animal interaction evolved can result in stabilising
22
23 648 eco-evolutionary feedbacks. In many ecosystems, fire controls plant population turnover and
24
25 649 promotes plant reproduction, which stabilises specialised plant-animal interactions such as
26
27 650 pollination [1, 211]. Fire can also limit antagonistic plant-animal interactions, stabilising
28
29 651 populations by reducing seed predation [139]. Reinforcing (positive) feedbacks occur when a
30
31 652 species forces a response in the environment which intensifies a change in population
32
33 653 dynamics, leading to local adaptation and further directional environmental change [209,
34
35 654 210]. A famous example of a reinforcing feedback implicated in fire regime shifts is the
36
37 655 invasion of high-biomass grasses [10, 11, 212]. When invasive grasses increase biomass and
38
39 656 flammability, fire activity can promote further invasion [10, 11, 212]. Traits promoting fire
40
41 657 tolerance and flammability in such grasses have evolved beyond the variability observed in
42
43 658 their native range [213, 214], suggesting that rapid evolutionary changes can feed back into
44
45 659 fire regimes.

46
47 660
48
49 661 Both stabilising and reinforcing eco-evolutionary feedbacks might be important in plant-
50
51 662 animal interactions, if the interaction modifies the environment, and the environment
52
53 663 influences the interaction through selection on species traits [51, 53, 215]. For mutualisms,
54
55 664 eco-evolutionary feedbacks generally result in co-evolution. However, partner switching,
56
57 665 interaction type switching (e.g., mutualism breakdown, resulting in a switch to antagonism)
58
59 666 and co-extinction have been documented when the evolutionary rate of one interaction
60
61 667 partner is slow, resulting in reduced fitness of the other interaction partner [51, 53]. Eco-
62
63 668 evolutionary feedbacks in commensalisms have also resulted in interaction type switches
64
65 669 (e.g., to mutualism or antagonism) [52]. However, these can be evolutionary endpoints for the
66
67 670 commensal interaction partner if they do not respond in a directional manner which matches
68
69 671 their interactors evolution [52]. Eco-evolutionary feedbacks in antagonistic interactions can

1
2
3 672 result in a range of outcomes including antagonism release, for example where predators fail
4 673 to evolve and prey are released from predation [216, 217]. Co-evolution of antagonisms can
5 674 also strengthen the interaction [216, 217]. As in other interaction types, co-extinction of
6 675 specialist predators can occur when the prey has low evolutionary potential, leading to
7 676 resource limitations for the predator [216, 217].
8
9

10
11
12 677

13 678 Research has revealed how fire-induced plant population dynamics can feed back into the fire
14 679 regime by changing ecosystem structure and strengthening selection on plant and animals in
15 680 fire-prone ecosystems (e.g., [25, 218, 219]). Animals are often implicated in these dynamics,
16 681 especially in the case of grazing herbivores [220, 221]. Grazing pressures and fire frequency
17 682 effects on plants are coupled, with preferential grazing in immediate post-fire environments
18 683 resulting in biomass reductions, further suppressing fire [220, 221]. When grazing pressure is
19 684 low, biomass increases and promotes fire occurrence and intensity [220, 221], which can also
20 685 determine where and how herbivores graze [220]. Few studies, however, have explicitly
21 686 investigated how fire influences eco-evolutionary dynamics in plant-animal interactions,
22 687 beyond vegetation structure. Exemplary research on this topic is demonstrated by the study of
23 688 serotiny in lodgepole pine, *P. contorta latifolia* and the seed predator American red squirrel,
24 689 *T. hudsonicus* [55, 56]. Conflicting directional selection occurs in this plant-animal
25 690 interaction: fire drives selection for serotiny, and pre-dispersal seed predation by the squirrel
26 691 drives selection against serotiny [55, 56]. Selection against serotiny in *P. contorta latifolia*
27 692 from seed predation is stronger than selection for serotiny from fire, but only where *T.*
28 693 *hudsonicus* is abundant [55, 56] resulting in landscape level variation in serotiny expression.
29 694 This state-of-the-art research can help us identify the potential for such dynamics in other
30 695 plant-animal interactions from fire-prone ecosystems. However, few studies have
31 696 investigated fire-related eco-evolutionary dynamics in as much detail as the squirrel-pine
32 697 example.
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47

48 698

49 699 **Conclusion**

50 700

51
52
53 701 Research on specialist plant-animal interactions in fire-prone ecosystems is a relatively new
54 702 field, but given current biodiversity declines as a result of global change it is vital to
55 703 understand these interactions. We identified a number of specialised mutualistic and
56 704 antagonistic interactions that affect, and are affected by, variation in fire regimes. Commensal
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 705 interactions were the most under-represented interaction type in our review and all of them
4
5 706 represented animal species specialising on a single plant genus. This was probably because
6
7 707 less is known about commensalism in general [52] and also because it was difficult to
8
9 708 identify specialist relationships from fire-prone ecosystems. Regardless, drawing together
10
11 709 literature on specialised plant-animal interactions allowed us to identify how fire regime
12
13 710 changes impact these interactions. This differs from previous work on plant- and animal-traits
14
15 711 generally in fire prone ecosystems (e.g., [22, 23, 27]), as we identified key plant- and animal-
16
17 712 traits that critically underlie specialist plant-animal interactions (figure 1). For plants these
18
19 713 traits include: reproductive mode, time to maturity, morphology, and phenology; and for
20
21 714 animals: dispersal ability, nesting substrate, egg deposition substrate, specialised physiology,
22
23 715 plant consumption behaviours, and pollination behaviours. As managing fire for conservation
24
25 716 outcomes is critical, this information could be used to adapt management plans to maximise
26
27 717 their suitability for the greatest biodiversity.

28
29 718
30
31 719 While we found widespread evidence for traits involved in plant-animal interactions under
32
33 720 strong selection pressure (e.g., post-fire reproduction mode), very few studies have
34
35 721 demonstrated fire-driven evolution on ecological timescales in plant-animal interactions. In
36
37 722 our review, the reinforcing nature of fire on plant-animal interactions was usually identified
38
39 723 to be rapid and result in abrupt changes in the state of the ecosystem. There is evidence that
40
41 724 the impact of evolution increases with increasing interaction strength for antagonisms and
42
43 725 with decreasing interaction strength for mutualisms [222]. Our review identified more traits
44
45 726 involved in mutualisms as being subjected to strong selection pressure (figure 1) than those
46
47 727 for antagonisms. However, this is more likely a result of the limited number of studies
48
49 728 published on this research topic rather than a biological outcome. Thus, it is clear that more
50
51 729 research is required to understand evolutionary changes on short time scales. Key to
52
53 730 understanding plant-animal interactions in fire prone ecosystems and the potential eco-
54
55 731 evolutionary feedbacks of fire on these interactions is a detailed knowledge of plant and
56
57 732 animal traits involved in fire responses. Our compilation of these traits (figure 1) represent
58
59 733 what has been researched to date, rather than a comprehensive list of the traits involved. In
60
734 some of these specialised interactions, we noted a bias towards focussing on the impacts that
735 fire has on the animal species, rather than the interaction itself. Given that plants are the
736 foundation of animal habitat, understanding plant responses is necessary for any study on
737 plant-animal interactions. However, future research in this area would benefit from reporting

1
2
3 738 the interactive effects of the animal species and fire on the plant species post-fire recovery as
4
5 739 this would aid effective conservation and management practices.
6
7 740

8 741 **Acknowledgements**

9
10 742
11
12 743 Craig Benkman, Luke Kelly, and Juli Pausas provided valuable feedback and ideas that
13
14 744 greatly improved the manuscript. Patrick Moss provided helpful guidance in the early
15
16 745 development of this manuscript. Jess Hopf assisted with figure production.
17
18 746

19 747 **Ethics**

20
21 748
22
23 749 This work did not require ethical approval from a human subject or animal welfare
24
25 750 committee.
26
27 751

28 752 **Use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and AI-assisted technologies**

29
30 753
31
32 754 The authors declare that we have not used AI-assisted technologies in creation of this article.
33
34 755

35 756 **Data, code, and materials**

36
37 757
38
39 758 No primary data were generated in the production of this manuscript. The Supplementary
40
41 759 Material contains information on the plant-animal interactions and plant species post-fire
42
43 760 reproductive mode cited in our literature review.
44
45 761

46 762 **Competing interests**

47
48 763
49
50 764 The authors declare that we have no competing interests.
51
52 765

53 766 **CRedit (Contributor Roles Taxonomy)**

54
55 767
56
57 768 Felicity E Charles (FEC): conceptualization (equal), data curation (lead), formal analysis
58
59 769 (lead), investigation (lead), methodologies (equal), visualization (equal), writing – original
60
770 draft preparation (lead), writing – reviewing and editing (equal). April E Reside (AER):

1
2
3 771 conceptualization (supporting), writing – reviewing and editing (equal). Annabel L Smith
4 (ALS): conceptualization (equal), data curation (supporting), investigation (supporting),
5 772 methodologies (equal), visualization (equal), writing – reviewing and editing (equal).
6 773
7

8
9 774 All authors read and approved the final manuscript.
10

11 775

12 776 **References**

13 777

14
15
16
17 778 1. Carbone, L. M., Tavella, J., Pausas, J. G. & Aguilar, R. 2019 A global synthesis of fire
18 779 effects on pollinators. *Glob Ecol Biogeogr* **28**, 1487-1498.

19
20 780 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/geb.12939>).
21

22 781

23
24 782 2. He, T., Lamont, B. B. & Pausas, J. G. 2019 Fire as a key driver of Earth's biodiversity. *Biol*
25 783 *Rev Camb Philos Soc* **94**, 1983-2010. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/brv.12544>).
26
27

28 784

29
30 785 3. Jones, G. M., Goldberg, J. F., Wilcox, T. M., Buckley, L. B., Parr, C. L., Linck, E. B.,
31 786 Fountain, E. D. & Schwartz, M. K. 2023 Fire-driven animal evolution in the Pyrocene.

32
33 787 *Trends Ecol Evol* **38**, 1072-1084. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2023.06.003>).
34

35 788

36
37 789 4. Kelly, L. T., Giljohann, K. M., Duane, A., Aquilue, N., Archibald, S., Batllori, E., Bennett,
38 790 A. F., Buckland, S. T., Canelles, Q., Clarke, M. F., et al. 2020 Fire and biodiversity in the
39 791 Anthropocene. *Science* **370**, 929. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abb0355>).
40
41
42

43 792

44
45 793 5. Driscoll, D. A., Armenteras, D., Bennett, A. F., Brotons, L., Clarke, M. F., Doherty, T. S.,
46 794 Haslem, A., Kelly, L. T., Sato, C. F., Sitters, H., et al. 2021 How fire interacts with habitat
47 795 loss and fragmentation. *Biol Rev* **96**, 976-998. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/brv.12687>).
48
49

50 796

51
52 797 6. González, T. M., González-Trujillo, J. D., Muñoz, A. & Armenteras, D. 2022 Effects of
53 798 fire history on animal communities: a systematic review. *Ecol Process* **11**, 11.

54
55 799 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13717-021-00357-7>).
56
57

58 800
59
60

- 1
2
3 801 7. Le Page, Y., Morton, D., Hartin, C., Bond-Lamberty, B., Pereira, J. M. C., Hurtt, G. &
4 802 Asrar, G. 2017 Synergy between land use and climate change increases future fire risk in
5 803 Amazon forests. *Earth Syst Dyn* **8**, 1237-1246. (DOI:[https://doi.org/10.5194/esd-8-1237-](https://doi.org/10.5194/esd-8-1237-2017)
6 804 [2017](https://doi.org/10.5194/esd-8-1237-2017)).
- 7
8
9
10
11 805
12 806 8. Dowdy, A. J., Ye, H., Pepler, A., Thatcher, M., Osbrough, S. L., Evans, J. P., Di Virgilio,
13 807 G. & McCarthy, N. 2019 Future changes in extreme weather and pyroconvection risk factors
14 808 for Australian wildfires. *Sci Rep* **9**, 10073-10011. (DOI:[https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-46362-x)
15 809 [46362-x](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-46362-x)).
- 16
17
18
19
20 810
21
22 811 9. Moritz, M. A., Parisien, M.-A., Batllori, E., Krawchuk, M. A., Van Dorn, J., Ganz, D. J. &
23 812 Hayhoe, K. 2012 Climate change and disruptions to global fire activity. *Ecosphere* **3**, art49.
24 813 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1890/ES11-00345.1>).
- 25
26
27
28 814
29 815 10. Brooks, M. L., D'Antonio, C. M., Richardson, D. M., Grace, J. B., Keeley, J. E.,
30 816 DiTomaso, J. M., Hobbs, R. J., Pellant, M. & Pyke, D. 2004 Effects of invasive alien plants
31 817 on fire regimes. *BioScience* **54**, 677-688. (DOI:[https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-](https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568(2004)054[0677:EOIAP0]2.0.CO;2)
32 818 [3568\(2004\)054\[0677:EOIAP0\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568(2004)054[0677:EOIAP0]2.0.CO;2)).
- 33
34
35
36
37 819
38
39 820 11. Setterfield, S. A., Rossiter-Rachor, N. A., Douglas, M. M., Wainger, L., Petty, A. M.,
40 821 Barrow, P., Shepherd, I. J. & Ferdinands, K. B. 2013 Adding fuel to the fire: the impacts of
41 822 non-native grass invasion on fire management at a regional scale. *PLoS One* **8**, e59144.
42 823 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0059144>).
- 43
44
45
46 824
47
48 825 12. Ruscalleda-Alvarez, J., Moro, D. & van Dongen, R. 2021 A multi-scale assessment of fire
49 826 scar mapping in the Great Victoria Desert of Western Australia. *Int J Wildland Fire* **30**, 886-
50 827 898. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1071/WF21019>).
- 51
52
53
54 828
55
56 829 13. Roos, C. I., Guiterman, C. H., Margolis, E. Q., Swetnam, T. W., Laluk, N. C., Thompson,
57 830 K. F., Toya, C., Farris, C. A., Fulé, P. Z., Iniguez, J. M., et al. 2022 Indigenous fire

- 1
2
3 831 management and cross-scale fire-climate relationships in the southwest United States from
4 832 1500 to 1900 CE. *Sci Adv* **8**, eabq3221. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abq3221>).
- 5
6
7 833
8
9 834 14. Le Goff, H., Flannigan, M. D. & Bergeron, Y. 2009 Potential changes in monthly fire risk
10 835 in the eastern Canadian boreal forest under future climate change. *Can J For Res* **39**, 2369-
11 836 2380. (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1139/X09-153>).
- 12
13
14
15 837
16 838 15. Moriondo, M., Good, P., Durao, R., Bindi, M., Giannakopoulos, C. & Corte-Real, J. 2006
17 839 Potential impact of climate change on fire risk in the Mediterranean area. *Clim Res* **31**, 85-95.
18 840 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.3354/cr031085>).
- 19
20
21
22 841
23
24 842 16. Becerra, J. X. 2003 Synchronous coadaptation in an ancient case of herbivory. *PNAS*
25 843 *Nexus* **100**, 12804-12807. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2133013100>).
- 26
27
28 844
29
30 845 17. Agrawal, A. A. 2000 Specificity of induced resistance in wild radish: causes and
31 846 consequences for two specialist and two generalist caterpillars. *Oikos* **89**, 493-500.
32 847 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1034/j.1600-0706.2000.890308.x>).
- 33
34
35
36 848
37
38 849 18. Santos, X., Mateos, E., Bros, V., Brotons, L., De Mas, E., Herraiz, J. A., Herrando, S.,
39 850 Miño, À., Olmo-Vidal, J. M., Quesada, J., et al. 2014 Is response to fire influenced by dietary
40 851 specialization and mobility? A comparative study with multiple animal assemblages. *PLoS*
41 852 *One* **9**, e88224. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0088224>).
- 42
43
44
45 853
46
47 854 19. Hammond, T. T., Palme, R. & Lacey, E. A. 2018 Ecological specialization, variability in
48 855 activity patterns and response to environmental change. *Biol Lett* **14**, 20180115.
49 856 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1098/rsbl.2018.0115>).
- 50
51
52
53 857
54
55 858 20. Harvey, B. J. & Enright, N. J. 2022 Climate change and altered fire regimes: impacts on
56 859 plant populations, species, and ecosystems in both hemispheres. *Plant Ecol* **223**, 699-709.
57 860 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11258-022-01248-3>).
- 58
59
60

- 1
2
3 861
4
5 862 21. Santos, J. L., Hradsky, B. A., Keith, D. A., Rowe, K. C., Senior, K. L., Sitters, H. &
6 863 Kelly, L. T. 2022 Beyond inappropriate fire regimes: a synthesis of fire-driven declines of
7 864 threatened mammals in Australia. *Conserv Lett* **15**, e12905.
8 865 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12905>).
9
10 866
11
12 867 22. Pausas, J. G., Bradstock, R. A., Keith, D. A. & Keeley, J. E. 2004 Plant functional traits
13 868 in relation to fire in crown-fire ecosystems. *Ecology* **85**, 1085-1100.
14 869 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1890/02-4094>).
15
16 870
17 871 23. Pausas, J. G. & Parr, C. L. 2018 Towards an understanding of the evolutionary role of fire
18 872 in animals. *Evol Ecol* **32**, 113-125. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10682-018-9927-6>).
19
20 873
21 874 24. Smith, A. L. 2018 Successional changes in trophic interactions support a mechanistic
22 875 model of post-fire population dynamics. *Oecologia* **186**, 129-139.
23 876 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-017-4016-z>).
24
25 877
26 878 25. Archibald, S., Lehmann, C. E. R., Belcher, C. M., Bond, W. J., Bradstock, R. A., Daniau,
27 879 A.-L., Dexter, K. G., Forrester, E. J., Greve, M., He, T., et al. 2018 Biological and
28 880 geophysical feedbacks with fire in the Earth system. *Environ Res Lett* **13**, 033003.
29 881 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aa9ead>).
30
31 882
32 883 26. Pausas, J. G. & Moreira, B. 2012 Flammability as a biological concept. *New Phytol* **194**,
33 884 610-613. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-8137.2012.04132.x>).
34
35 885
36 886 27. Keith, D. A. 2012 Functional traits: their roles in understanding and predicting biotic
37 887 responses to fire regimes from individuals to landscapes. In *Flammable Australia: fire*
38 888 *regimes, biodiversity and ecosystems in a changing world* (eds. R. A. Bradstock, A. M. Gill
39 889 & R. J. Williams), pp. 97-125. Victoria, Australia, CSIRO Publishing.
40
41 890
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 891 28. Pausas, J. G. 2019 Generalized fire response strategies in plants and animals. *Oikos* **128**,
4 892 147-153. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/oik.05907>).
5
6
7 893
8
9 894 29. Zimmer, H., Allen, J., Smith, R., Gibson, R. & Auld, T. 2021 Post-fire recruitment and
10 895 resprouting of a threatened montane eucalypt. *Aust J Bot* **69**, 21-29.
11
12 896 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1071/BT20116>).
13
14
15 897
16 898 30. Smith, A. L., Blanchard, W., Blair, D. P., McBurney, L., Banks, S. C., Driscoll, D. A. &
17 899 Lindenmayer, D. B. 2016 The dynamic regeneration niche of a forest following a rare
18 900 disturbance event. *Divers Distrib* **22**, 457-467. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.12414>).
19
20
21
22 901
23
24 902 31. Plumanns-Pouton, E. S., Swan, M. H., Penman, T. D., Collins, L. & Kelly, L. T. 2023
25 903 Time since fire shapes plant immaturity risk across fire severity classes. *Fire Ecol.* **19**, 13.
26 904 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s42408-023-00185-4>).
27
28
29
30 905
31
32 906 32. Gosper, C. R., Watson, S. J., Fox, E., Burbidge, A. H., Craig, M. D., Douglas, T. K.,
33 907 Fitzsimons, J. A., McNee, S., Nicholls, A. O., O'Connor, J., et al. 2019 Fire-mediated habitat
34 908 change regulates woodland bird species and functional group occurrence. *Ecol Appl* **29**,
35 909 e01997. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1002/eap.1997>).
36
37
38
39 910
40
41 911 33. Rainsford, F. W., Kelly, L. T., Leonard, S. W. J. & Bennett, A. F. 2020 Post-fire
42 912 development of faunal habitat depends on plant regeneration traits. *Austral Ecol* **45**, 800-812.
43 913 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/aec.12896>).
44
45
46
47 914
48
49 915 34. Foster, C. N., Banks, S. C., Cary, G. J., Johnson, C. N., Lindenmayer, D. B. & Valentine,
50 916 L. E. 2020 Animals as agents in fire regimes. *Trends Ecol Evol* **35**, 346-356.
51 917 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2020.01.002>).
52
53
54 918
55
56 919 35. García, Y., Clara Castellanos, M. & Pausas, J. G. 2018 Differential pollinator response
57 920 underlies plant reproductive resilience after fires. *Ann Bot* **122**, 961-971.
58 921 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1093/aob/mcy122>).
59
60

- 1
2
3 922
4
5 923 36. Archibald, S. & Hempson, G. P. 2016 Competing consumers: contrasting the patterns and
6 924 impacts of fire and mammalian herbivory in Africa. *Philos Trans R Soc B* **371**, 20150309.
7
8 925 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2015.0309>).
9
10 926
11
12 927 37. Ballarin, C. S., Mores, G. J., Alcarás de Goés, G., Fidelis, A. & Cornelissen, T. 2024
13 928 Trends and gaps in the study of fire effects on plant–animal interactions in Brazilian
14 929 ecosystems. *Austral Ecol* **49**, e13420. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/aec.13420>).
15
16
17 930
18
19 931 38. Sexton, J. P., Montiel, J., Shay, J. E., Stephens, M. R. & Slatyer, R. A. 2017 Evolution of
20 932 ecological niche breadth. *Annu Rev Ecol Evol Syst* **48**, 183-206.
21
22 933 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-ecolsys-110316-023003>).
23
24 934
25
26 935 39. Li, S., Jovelin, R., Yoshiga, T., Tanaka, R. & Cutter, A. D. 2014 Specialist versus
27 936 generalist life histories and nucleotide diversity in *Caenorhabditis* nematodes. *Proc Biol Sci*
28 937 **281**, 20132858. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2013.2858>).
29
30
31 938
32
33 939 40. von Meijenfeldt, F. A. B., Hogeweg, P. & Dutilh, B. E. 2023 A social niche breadth score
34 940 reveals niche range strategies of generalists and specialists. *Nat Ecol Evol* **7**, 768-781.
35
36 941 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-023-02027-7>).
37
38 942
39
40 943 41. Pasinelli, G. 2022 Genetic diversity and spatial genetic structure support the specialist-
41 944 generalist variation hypothesis in two sympatric woodpecker species. *Conserv Genet* **23**, 821-
42 945 837. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10592-022-01451-9>).
43
44
45 946
46
47 947 42. Bono, L. M., Draghi, J. A. & Turner, P. E. 2020 Evolvability costs of niche expansion.
48 948 *Trends Genet* **36**, 14-23. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tig.2019.10.003>).
49
50
51 949
52
53 950 43. Malcom, J. W. 2011 Smaller gene networks permit longer persistence in fast-changing
54 951 environments. *PLoS One* **6**, e14747. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0014747>).
55
56
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 952
4
5 953 44. Sachdeva, V., Husain, K., Sheng, J., Wang, S. & Murugan, A. 2020 Tuning
6 954 environmental timescales to evolve and maintain generalists. *PNAS Nexus* **117**, 12693-12699.
7
8 955 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1914586117>).
9
10 956
11
12 957 45. Kassen, R. 2002 The experimental evolution of specialists, generalists, and the
13 958 maintenance of diversity. *J Evol Biol* **15**, 173-190. (DOI:[https://doi.org/10.1046-](https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1420-9101.2002.00377.x)
14 959 [9101.2002.00377.x](https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1420-9101.2002.00377.x)).
15
16 960
17
18 961 46. Poisot, T., Bever, J. D., Nemri, A., Thrall, P. H. & Hochberg, M. E. 2011 A conceptual
19 962 framework for the evolution of ecological specialisation. *Ecol Lett* **14**, 841-851.
20 963 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2011.01645.x>).
21
22 964
23
24 965 47. Hanski, I. 2012 Eco-evolutionary dynamics in a changing world. *Ann N Y Acad Sci* **1249**,
25 966 1-17. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-6632.2011.06419.x>).
26
27 967
28
29 968 48. Chichorro, F., Juslén, A. & Cardoso, P. 2019 A review of the relation between species
30 969 traits and extinction risk. *Biol Conserv* **237**, 220-229.
31 970 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2019.07.001>).
32
33 971
34
35 972 49. Biesmeijer, J. C., Roberts, S. P. M., Reemer, M., Ohlemüller, R., Edwards, M., Peeters,
36 973 T., Schaffers, A. P., Potts, S. G., Kleukers, R., Thomas, C. D., et al. 2006 Parallel declines in
37 974 pollinators and insect-pollinated plants in Britain and the Netherlands. *Science* **313**, 351-354.
38 975 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1127863>).
39
40 976
41
42 977 50. Clavel, J., Julliard, R. & Devictor, V. 2011 Worldwide decline of specialist species:
43 978 toward a global functional homogenization? *Front Ecol Environ* **9**, 222-228.
44 979 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1890/080216>).
45
46
47
48
49 980
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 981 51. Weinbach, A., Loeuille, N. & Rohr, R. P. 2022 Eco-evolutionary dynamics further
4 982 weakens mutualistic interaction and coexistence under population decline. *Evol Ecol* **36**, 373-
5 983 387. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10682-022-10176-7>).
6
7
8
9 984
10
11 985 52. Mathis, K. A. & Bronstein, J. L. 2020 Our current understanding of commensalism. *Annu*
12 986 *Rev Ecol Evol Syst* **51**, 167-189. (DOI:[https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-ecolsys-011720-](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-ecolsys-011720-040844)
13 987 [040844](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-ecolsys-011720-040844)).
14
15
16 988
17
18 989 53. Weyerer, F., Weinbach, A., Zarfl, C. & Allhoff, K. T. 2023 Eco-evolutionary dynamics in
19 990 two-species mutualistic systems: one-sided population decline triggers joint interaction
20 991 disinvestment. *Evol Ecol* **37**, 981-999. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10682-023-10264-2>).
21
22
23
24 992
25
26 993 54. Hutchinson, M. C., Dobson, A. P. & Pringle, R. M. 2022 Dietary abundance distributions:
27 994 dominance and diversity in vertebrate diets. *Ecol Lett* **25**, 992-1008.
28 995 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.13948>).
29
30
31
32 996
33
34 997 55. Talluto, M. V. & Benkman, C. W. 2013 Landscape-scale eco-evolutionary dynamics:
35 998 selection by seed predators and fire determine a major reproductive strategy. *Ecology* **94**,
36 999 1307-1316. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1890/12-2058.1>).
37
38
39 1000
40
41 1001 56. Talluto, M. V. & Benkman, C. W. 2014 Conflicting selection from fire and seed
42 1002 predation drives fine-scaled phenotypic variation in a widespread North American conifer.
43 1003 *PNAS Nexus* **111**, 9543-9548. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1400944111>).
44
45
46
47 1004
48
49 1005 57. Del-Claro, K. & Torezan-Silingardi, H. M. 2021 An evolutionary perspective on plant-
50 1006 animal interactions. In *Plant-animal interactions source of biodiversity* (eds. K. Del-Claro &
51 1007 H. M. Torezan-Silingardi), pp. 1-15, 1st ed. Switzerland, Springer Publishing.
52
53
54 1008
55
56 1009 58. Westgate, M. J. 2019 revtools: an R package to support article screening for evidence
57 1010 synthesis. *Res Synth Methods* **10**, 606-614. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1002/jrsm.1374>).
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 1011
4
5 1012 59. R Core Team. 2020 The R Project for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical
6 1013 Computing. Viewed 12th September 2020, <<https://www.r-project.org>>.
7
8
9 1014
10
11 1015 60. Brown, S. M., Harrison, K. A., Clarke, R. H., Bennett, A. F. & Sunnucks, P. 2013
12 1016 Limited population structure, genetic drift and bottlenecks characterise an endangered bird
13 1017 species in a dynamic, fire-prone ecosystem. *PLoS One* **8**, e59732.
14 1018 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0059732>).
15
16 1019
17
18 1020
19
20 1020 61. Australian Surveying and Land Information Group. 1980 *Atlas of Australian*
21 1021 *resources*. eds. F. Bullen, J. Carnahan & T. Deveson. Canberra, Australian Capital Territory,
22 1022 Australia, Australian Surveying and Land Information Group (AUSLIG), Department of
23 1023 Administrative Services.
24
25 1024
26
27 1025
28
29 1025 62. Kattge, J. & Bönisch, G. & Díaz, S. & Lavorel, S. & Prentice, I. C. & Leadley, P. &
30 1026 Tautenhahn, S. & Werner, G. D. A. & Aakala, T. & Abedi, M., et al. 2020 TRY plant trait
31 1027 database - enhanced coverage and open access. *Glob Chang Biol* **26**, 119-188.
32 1028 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14904>).
33
34 1029
35
36 1030
37
38 1030 63. Falster, D. & Gallagher, R. & Wenk, E. H. & Wright, I. J. & Indiarito, D. & Andrew, S. C.
39 1031 & Baxter, C. & Lawson, J. & Allen, S. & Fuchs, A., et al. 2021 AusTraits, a curated plant
40 1032 trait database for the Australian flora. *Sci Data* **8**. (DOI:[https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-021-](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-021-01006-6)
41 1033 [01006-6](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-021-01006-6)).
42
43 1034
44
45 1035
46
47 1035 64. Tavşanoğlu, Ç. & Pausas, J. G. 2018 A functional trait database for Mediterranean Basin
48 1036 plants. *Sci Data* **5**, 180135. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2018.135>).
49
50 1037
51
52 1038
53
54 1038 65. United States of America Department of Agriculture - Forest Service. 2023 Fire Effects
55 1039 Information System (FEIS). United States of America U. S. Department of Agriculture,
56 1040 Forest Service, Rocky Mountain Research Station, Fire Sciences Laboratory. Viewed 22
57 1041 January 2024, <<https://www.feis-crs.org/feis/>>.
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 1042
4
5 1043 66. Glasier, J. R. N., Poore, A. G. B. & Eldridge, D. J. 2018 Do mutualistic associations have
6
7 1044 broader host ranges than neutral or antagonistic associations? A test using myrmecophiles as
8
9 1045 model organisms. *Insect Soc* **65**, 639-648. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00040-018-0655-2>).
- 10
11 1046
12 1047 67. Dufaÿ, M. & Anstett, M. C. 2004 Cheating is not always punished: killer female plants
13
14 1048 and pollination by deceit in the dwarf palm *Chamaerops humilis*. *J Evol Biol* **17**, 862-868.
15
16 1049 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1420-9101.2004.00714.x>).
- 17
18 1050
19
20 1051 68. Anstett, M. C. 1999 An experimental study of the interaction between the dwarf palm
21
22 1052 (*Chamaerops humilis*) and its floral visitor *Derelomus chamaeropsis* throughout the life cycle
23
24 1053 of the weevil. *Acta Oecol* **20**, 551-558. (DOI:[https://doi.org/10.1016/S1146-609X\(00\)86622-](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1146-609X(00)86622-9)
25 1054 [9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1146-609X(00)86622-9)).
- 26
27 1055
28
29 1056 69. Dufaÿ, M., Hossaert-McKey, M. & Anstett, M. C. 2003 When leaves act like flowers:
30
31 1057 how dwarf palms attract their pollinators. *Ecol Lett* **6**, 28-34.
32
33 1058 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1461-0248.2003.00382.x>).
- 34
35 1059
36
37 1060 70. Santiesteban, E., Ple, C. G. & Morey, M. 1992 Postfire phenology of *Chamaerops*
38
39 1061 *humilis* L. in a Mediterranean-type shrubland. In *Responses of Forest Ecosystems to*
40
41 1062 *Environmental Changes* (eds. A. Teller, P. Mathy & J. N. R. Jeffers), pp. 851-852. Dordrecht,
42 1063 Springer Netherlands.
- 43
44 1064
45
46 1065 71. Lybbert, A. H. & St. Clair, S. B. 2016 Wildfire and floral herbivory alter reproduction
47
48 1066 and pollinator mutualisms of Yuccas and Yucca moths. *J Plant Ecol* **10**, 851-858. (DOI:
49 1067 <https://doi.org/10.1093/jpe/rtw077>).
- 50
51 1068
52
53 1069 72. Lybbert, A. H., Taylor, J., Defranco, A. & St Clair, S. B. 2017 Reproductive success of
54
55 1070 wind, generalist, and specialist pollinated plant species following wildfire in desert
56
57 1071 landscapes. *Int J Wildland Fire* **26**, 1030-1039. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1071/WF16222>).
- 58
59 1072
60

- 1
2
3 1073 73. Powell, J. A. 1992 Interrelationships of Yuccas and Yucca moths. *Trends Ecol Evol* **7**,
4 1074 10-15. (DOI:[https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-5347\(92\)90191-D](https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-5347(92)90191-D)).
5
6
7 1075
8
9 1076 74. Warren, S. D., Baggett, L. S. & Warren, H. 2016 Directional floral orientation in Joshua
10 1077 trees (*Yucca brevifolia*). *West N Am Nat* **76**, 374-378.
11
12 1078 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.3398/064.076.0313>).
13
14
15 1079
16 1080 75. Pellmyr, O. 2003 Yuccas, Yucca moths, and coevolution: a review. *Ann Mo Bot Gard* **90**,
17 1081 35-55. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.2307/3298524>).
18
19 1082
20
21 1083 76. DeFalco, L. A., Esque, T. C., Scoles-Sciulla, S. J. & Rodgers, J. 2010 Desert wildfire and
22 1084 severe drought diminish survivorship of the long-lived Joshua tree (*Yucca brevifolia*;
23 1085 Agavaceae). *Am J Bot* **97**, 243-250. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.3732/ajb.0900032>).
24
25
26 1086
27
28 1087 77. McGoldrick, T. A. 1994 Effects of fire on four desert plants: *Dasylyrion wheeleri*,
29 1088 *Ferocactus wislizeni*, *Yucca baccata*, and *Yucca torreyi* [Master of Science, Department of
30 1089 Biological Sciences]. Texas, United States of America, The University of Texas.
31
32
33
34 1090
35
36 1091 78. Buchmann, S. L. 1987 The ecology of oil flowers and their bees. *Annu Rev Ecol Syst* **18**,
37 1092 343-369. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.es.18.110187.002015>).
38
39
40 1093
41
42 1094 79. Giannini, T. C., Pinto, C. E., Acosta, A. L., Taniguchi, M., Saraiva, A. M. & Alves-dos-
43 1095 Santos, I. 2013 Interactions at large spatial scale: The case of *Centris* bees and floral oil
44 1096 producing plants in South America. *Ecol Model* **258**, 74-81.
45
46 1097 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2013.02.032>).
47
48
49 1098
50
51 1099 80. Griffith, R. S. 1991 *Krameria grayi*. In: Fire Effects Information System. United States of
52 1100 America U. S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, Rocky Mountain Research Station,
53 1101 Fire Sciences Laboratory. Viewed 22 January 2024,
54 1102 <<https://www.fs.usda.gov/database/feis/plants/shrub/kragra/all.html>>.
55
56
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 1103
4
5 1104 81. Pratt, R. B., Jacobsen, A. L., Ramirez, A. R., Helms, A. M., Traugh, C. A., Tobin, M. F.,
6 1105 Heffner, M. S. & Davis, S. D. 2014 Mortality of resprouting chaparral shrubs after a fire and
7 1106 during a record drought: physiological mechanisms and demographic consequences. *Glob*
8 1107 *Chang Biol* **20**, 893-907. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12477>).
9
10
11
12 1108
13
14 1109 82. Pausas, J. G., Pratt, R. B., Keeley, J. E., Jacobsen, A. L., Ramirez, A. R., Vilagrosa, A.,
15 1110 Paula, S., Kaneakua-Pia, I. N. & Davis, S. D. 2016 Towards understanding resprouting at the
16 1111 global scale. *New Phytol* **209**, 945-954. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.13644>).
17
18
19
20 1112
21
22 1113 83. Renner, S. S. & Schaefer, H. 2010 The evolution and loss of oil-offering flowers: new
23 1114 insights from dated phylogenies for angiosperms and bees. *Philos Trans R Soc Lond B Biol*
24 1115 *Sci* **365**, 423-435. (DOI:10.1098/rstb.2009.0229).
25
26
27
28 1116
29 1117 84. Oliveira, L. C., Nunes, C. E. P., Brito, V. L. G. & Caetano, A. P. S. 2022 Floral oil
30 1118 production in a family dominated by pollen flowers: the case of *Macairea radula*
31 1119 (Melastomataceae). *Flora* **288**, 152008. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.flora.2022.152008>).
32
33
34
35 1120
36
37 1121 85. Carneiro, L. T., Aguiar, A. J. C., Martins, C. F., Machado, I. C. & Alves-dos-Santos, I.
38 1122 2015 *Krameria tomentosa* oil flowers and their pollinators: bees specialized on trichome
39 1123 elaiophores exploit its epithelial oil glands. *Flora* **215**, 1-8.
40 1124 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.flora.2015.06.002>).
41
42
43
44 1125
45
46 1126 86. Love, B. G. & Cane, J. H. 2016 Limited direct effects of a massive wildfire on its
47 1127 sagebrush steppe bee community. *Ecol Entomol* **41**, 317-326.
48 1128 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/een.12304>).
49
50
51
52 1129
53
54 1130 87. Susic Martin, C. & Farina, W. M. 2016 Honeybee floral constancy and pollination
55 1131 efficiency in sunflower (*Helianthus annuus*) crops for hybrid seed production. *Apidologie* **47**,
56 1132 161-170. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13592-015-0384-8>).
57
58
59
60 1133

- 1
2
3 1134 88. de Paiva, G. J., Terada, Y. & De Alencar Arnaut de Toledo, V. 2003 Seed production and
4 1135 germination of sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) in three pollination systems. *Acta Sci -*
5 1136 *Anim Sci* **25**, 223-227. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.4025/actascianimsci.v25i2.1974>).
6
7
8
9 1137
10 1138 89. Praz, C. J., Müller, A. & Dorn, S. 2008 Host recognition in a pollen-specialist bee:
11 1139 evidence for a genetic basis. *Apidologie* **39**, 547-557.
12 1140 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1051/apido:2008034>).
13
14 1141
15
16 1142 90. Vanderplanck, M., Vereecken, N. J., Grumiau, L., Esposito, F., Lognay, G., Wattiez, R.
17 1143 & Michez, D. 2017 The importance of pollen chemistry in evolutionary host shifts of bees.
18 1144 *Sci Rep* **7**, 43058. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1038/srep43058>).
19
20
21
22
23 1145
24
25 1146 91. Sipes, S. D. & Wolf, P. G. 2001 Phylogenetic relationships within *Diadasia*, a group of
26 1147 specialist bees. *Mol Phylogenetics Evol* **19**, 144-156.
27 1148 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1006/mpev.2001.0914>).
28
29
30 1149
31
32 1150 92. Sipes, S. D. & Tepedino, V. J. 2005 Pollen-host specificity and evolutionary patterns of
33 1151 host switching in a clade of specialist bees (Apoidea: *Diadasia*). *Biol J Linn Soc Lond* **86**,
34 1152 487-505. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-8312.2005.00544.x>).
35
36
37
38 1153
39
40 1154 93. Love, B. G. & Cane, J. H. 2019 Mortality and flowering of Great Basin perennial forbs
41 1155 after experimental burning: implications for wild bees. *Range Ecol Manag* **72**, 310-317.
42 1156 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rama.2018.11.001>).
43
44
45
46 1157
47
48 1158 94. Wilson, P., Wolfe, A. D., Armbruster, W. S. & Thomson, J. D. 2007 Constrained lability
49 1159 in floral evolution: counting convergent origins of hummingbird pollination in *Penstemon*
50 1160 and *Keckiella*. *New Phytol* **176**, 883-890. (DOI:[https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-8137.2007.02219.x)
51 1161 [8137.2007.02219.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-8137.2007.02219.x)).
52
53
54
55 1162
56
57 1163 95. Alexander, J. D., Williams, E. J., Gillespie, C. R., Contreras-Martínez, S. & Finch, D. M.
58 1164 2020 Effects of restoration and fire on habitats and populations of western hummingbirds: a

1
2
3 1165 literature review. U.S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, Rocky Mountain Research
4 1166 Station, General Technical Report No. 1. (United States of America.) Viewed 30 May 2024,
5
6 1167 <<http://dx.doi.org/10.2737/RMRS-GTR-408>>.

8
9 1168
10 1169 96. Cane, J. H., Weber, M. & Love, B. G. 2020 Self-compatibility in *Lomatium dissectum*
11 1170 (Apiaceae) and the diverse *Andrena* bees that dominate regional *Lomatium* pollinator faunas.
12 1171 *West N Am Nat* **80**, 1-10. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.3398/064.080.0101>).

13 1172
14 1173 97. Cane, J. H. & Love, B. G. 2016 Floral guilds of bees in sagebrush steppe: comparing bee
15 1174 usage of wildflowers available for postfire restoration. *Nat Areas J* **36**, 377-391.
16 1175 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.3375/043.036.0405>).

17 1176
18 1177 98. Scholten, M., Donahue, J., Shaw, N. L. & Serpe, M. D. 2009 Environmental regulation of
19 1178 dormancy loss in seeds of *Lomatium dissectum* (Apiaceae). *Ann Bot* **103**, 1091-1101.
20 1179 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1093/aob/mcp038>).

21 1180
22 1181 99. Innes, R. J. & Zouhar, K. 2018 Fire regimes of mountain big sagebrush communities. In:
23 1182 Fire Effects Information System. United States of America U. S. Department of Agriculture,
24 1183 Forest Service, Rocky Mountain Reserach Station, Missoula Fire Sciences Laboratory.
25 1184 Viewed 25 January 2024,
26 1185 <https://www.fs.usda.gov/database/feis/fire_regimes/mountain_big_sagebrush/all.html#Prese
27 1186 [ttementFireSeason](https://www.fs.usda.gov/database/feis/fire_regimes/mountain_big_sagebrush/all.html#Prese)>.

28 1187
29 1188 100. White, J. D. M. & Midgley, J. J. 2017 Dispersal of semi-fleshy fruits to rock crevices by
30 1189 a rock-restricted rodent. *S Afr J Sci* **113**, 1-5.
31 1190 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.17159/sajs.2017/20170159>).

32 1191
33 1192 101. Burger, N. & Bond, W. J. 2015 Flammability traits of Cape shrubland species with
34 1193 different post-fire recruitment strategies. *S Afr J Bot* **101**, 40-48.
35 1194 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sajb.2015.05.026>).

36 1195

- 1
2
3 1196 102. De Omena, P. M., Kersch-Becker, M. F., Antiqueira, P. A. P., Bernabé, T. N.,
4 1197 Benavides-Gordillo, S., Recalde, F. C., Vieira, C., Migliorini, G. H. & Romero, G. Q. 2018
5 1198 Bromeliads provide shelter against fire to mutualistic spiders in a fire-prone landscape. *Ecol*
6 1199 *Entomol* **43**, 389-393. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/een.12497>).
- 10 1200
11 1201 103. Janzen, D. H. 1967 Fire, vegetation structure, and the ant x acacia interaction in Central
12 1202 America. *Ecology* **48**, 26-35. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.2307/1933414>).
- 16 1203
17 1204 104. Sensenig, R. L., Kimuyu, D. K., Guajardo, J. C. R., Veblen, K. E., Riginos, C. & Young,
18 1205 T. P. 2017 Fire disturbance disrupts an acacia ant-plant mutualism in favor of a subordinate
19 1206 ant species. *Ecology* **98**, 1455-1464. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1002/ecy.1797>).
- 23 1207
24 1208 105. Kimuyu, D. M., Sensenig, R. L., Riginos, C., Veblen, K. E. & Young, T. P. 2014 Native
25 1209 and domestic browsers and grazers reduce fuels, fire temperatures, and acacia ant mortality in
26 1210 an African savanna. *Ecol Appl* **24**, 741-749. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1890/13-1135.1>).
- 31 1211
32 1212 106. LaMalfa, E. M., Kimuyu, D. M., Sensenig, R. L., Young, T. P., Riginos, C. & Veblen,
33 1213 K. E. 2019 Tree resprout dynamics following fire depend on herbivory by wild ungulate
34 1214 herbivores. *J Ecol* **107**, 2493-2502. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2745.13186>).
- 38 1215
39 1216 107. Pringle, R. M., Prior, K. M., Palmer, T. M., Young, T. P. & Goheen, J. R. 2016 Large
40 1217 herbivores promote habitat specialization and beta diversity of African savanna trees.
41 1218 *Ecology* **97**, 2640-2657. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1002/ecy.1522>).
- 46 1219
47 1220 108. Romero, G. Q., Mazzafera, P., Vasconcellos-Neto, J. & Trivelin, P. C. O. 2006
48 1221 Bromeliad-living spiders improve host plant nutrition and growth. *Ecology* **87**, 803-808.
49 1222 (DOI:[https://doi.org/10.1890/0012-9658\(2006\)87\[803:bsihpn\]2.0.co;2](https://doi.org/10.1890/0012-9658(2006)87[803:bsihpn]2.0.co;2)).
- 53 1223
54 1224 109. Govender, N., Trollope, W. S. W. & Van Wilgen, B. W. 2006 The effect of fire season,
55 1225 fire frequency, rainfall and management on fire intensity in savanna vegetation in South
56 1226 Africa. *J Appl Ecol* **43**, 748-758. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2664.2006.01184.x>).

- 1
2
3 1227
4
5 1228 110. Damasceno-Junior, G. A., Pereira, A. d. M. M., Oldeland, J., Parolin, P. & Pott, A. 2021
6 1229 Fire, flood and Pantanal vegetation. In *Flora and vegetation of the Pantanal wetland* (eds. G.
7 1230 A. Damasceno-Junior & A. Pott), pp. 661-688. Switzerland, Springer International
8 1231 Publishing.
9
10 1232
11
12 1233 111. Gonçalves, A. Z., Mercier, H., Mazzafera, P. & Romero, G. Q. 2011 Spider-fed
13 1234 bromeliads: seasonal and interspecific variation in plant performance. *Ann Bot* **107**, 1047-
14 1235 1055. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1093/aob/mcr047>).
15
16 1236
17
18 1237 112. Ariani, C., Menezes, V. A., Vrcibradic, D., Carlos & Rocha, C. F. D. 2004 The negative
19 1238 effect of fire on populations of three bromeliad species at a restinga habitat in the southern
20 1239 state of Santa Catarina, Brazil. *Vidalia* **2**, 44-48.
21
22 1240
23
24 1241 113. Rocha, C. F. D., Van Sluys, M., Ornellas, A. E., Siqueira, A., Conde, C., Bittencourt, E.,
25 1242 Oliveira, M., Barros, M. & Magalhães, S. 1996 The effect of fire on natural populations of
26 1243 *Vriesea neoglutinosa* (Bromeliaceae) in a relict restinga of Espírito Santo State, Southeastern
27 1244 Brazil. *Revista Bromélia* **3**, 16-26.
28
29 1245
30
31 1246 114. Janzen, D. H. 1966 Coevolution of mutualism between ants and acacias in Central
32 1247 America. *Evolution* **20**, 249-275. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.2307/2406628>).
33
34 1248
35
36 1249 115. Pringle, R. M., Kimuyu, D. M., Sensenig, R. L., Palmer, T. M., Riginos, C., Veblen, K.
37 1250 E. & Young, T. P. 2015 Synergistic effects of fire and elephants on arboreal animals in an
38 1251 African savanna. *J Anim Ecol* **84**, 1637-1645. (DOI:[https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-](https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2656.12404)
39 1252 [2656.12404](https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2656.12404)).
40
41 1253
42
43 1254 116. Divekar, P. A., Narayana, S., Divekar, B. A., Kumar, R., Gadratagi, B. G., Ray, A.,
44 1255 Singh, A. K., Rani, V., Singh, V., Singh, A. K., et al. 2022 Plant secondary metabolites as
45 1256 defense tools against herbivores for sustainable crop protection. *Int J Mol Sci* **23**, 2690.
46 1257 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.3390/2Fijms23052690>).
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 1258
4
5 1259 117. Harris, P. L. & Stewart, D. 2009 Grasswren *Amytornis dorotheae* surveys near Mt Isa
6
7 1260 (1990 - 1995). *Sunbird* **39**, 3-13.
8
9 1261
10
11 1262 118. Stoetzel, H. J., Leseberg, N. P., Murphy, S. A., Andrew, M. E., Plant, K. J., Harrington,
12
13 1263 G. N. & Watson, J. E. M. 2020 Modelling the habitat of the endangered Carpentarian
14
15 1264 Grasswren (*Amytornis dorotheae*): the importance of spatio-temporal habitat availability in a
16
17 1265 fire prone landscape. *Glob Ecol Conserv* **24**, e01341.
18 1266 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2020.e01341>).
19
20 1267
21
22 1268 119. Harrington, G. N. & Murphy, S. A. 2015 The distribution and conservation status of
23
24 1269 Carpentarian Grasswrens (*Amytornis dorotheae*), with reference to prevailing fire patterns.
25
26 1270 *Pac Conserv Biol* **21**, 291-297. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1071/PC15021>).
27
28 1271
29
30 1272 120. Perry, J., Fisher, A. & Palmer, C. 2011 Status and habitat of the Carpentarian Grasswren
31
32 1273 (*Amytornis dorotheae*) in the Northern Territory. *Emu* **111**, 155-161.
33 1274 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1071/MU10013>).
34
35 1275
36
37 1276 121. Verdon, S. J., Watson, S. J. & Clarke, M. F. 2019 Modeling variability in the fire
38
39 1277 response of an endangered bird to improve fire-management. *Ecol Appl* **29**, e01980.
40
41 1278 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1002/eap.1980>).
42
43 1279
44
45 1280 122. Connell, J., Watson, S. J., Taylor, R. S., Avitabile, S. C., Clarke, R. H., Bennett, A. F. &
46
47 1281 Clarke, M. F. 2017 Testing the effects of a century of fires: requirements for post-fire
48
49 1282 succession predict the distribution of threatened bird species. *Divers Distrib* **23**, 1078-1089.
50 1283 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.12597>).
51
52 1284
53
54 1285 123. Brown, S., Clarke, M. F. & Clarke, R. H. 2009 Fire is a key element in the landscape-
55
56 1286 scale habitat requirements and global population status of a threatened bird: the Mallee Emu-
57
58 1287 wren (*Stipiturus mallee*). *Biol Conserv* **142**, 432-445.
59 1288 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2008.11.005>).
60

- 1
2
3 1289
4
5 1290 124. Noske, R. A. 1992 The status and ecology of the white-throated grasswren *Amytornis*
6 1291 *woodwardi*. *Emu* **92**, 39-51. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1071/MU9920039>).
7
8
9 1292
10
11 1293 125. Wright, B. R. & Fensham, R. J. 2018 Fire timing in relation to masting: an important
12 1294 determinant of post-fire recruitment success for the obligate-seeding arid zone soft spinifex
13 1295 (*Triodia pungens*). *Ann Bot* **121**, 119-128. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1093/aob/mcx136>).
14
15
16 1296
17
18 1297 126. Rice, B. & Westoby., M. 1999 Regeneration after fire in *Triodia* R. Br. *Austral Ecol* **24**,
19 1298 563-572. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1442-9993.1999.01004.x>).
20
21
22 1299
23
24 1300 127. Giljohann, K. M., McCarthy, M. A., Keith, D. A., Kelly, L. T., Tozer, M. G. & Regan,
25 1301 T. J. 2017 Interactions between rainfall, fire and herbivory drive resprouter vital rates in a
26 1302 semi-arid ecosystem. *J Ecol* **105**, 1562-1570. (DOI:[https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-](https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2745.12768)
27
28 1303 [2745.12768](https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2745.12768)).
29
30
31 1304
32
33 1305 128. Noble, J. C. & Vines, R. G. 1993 Fire studies in mallee (*Eucalyptus* spp.) communities
34 1306 of western New South Wales: grass fuel dynamics and associated weather patterns. *Rangel J*
35 1307 **15**, 270-297. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1071/RJ9930270>).
36
37
38 1308
39
40 1309 129. Mitchell, W. F., Boulton, R. L., Ireland, L., Hunt, T. J., Verdon, S. J., Olds, L. G. M.,
41 1310 Hedger, C. & Clarke, R. H. 2022 Using experimental trials to improve translocation protocols
42 1311 for a cryptic, endangered passerine. *Pac Conserv Biol* **28**, 68-79.
43 1312 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1071/PC20097>).
44
45
46 1313
47
48 1314 130. Kelly, L. T., Bennett, A. F., Clarke, M. F. & McCarthy, M. A. 2015 Optimal fire
49 1315 histories for biodiversity conservation. *Conserv Biol* **29**, 473-481.
50 1316 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.12384>).
51
52
53 1317
54
55 1318 131. Driscoll, D. A. & Henderson, M. K. 2008 How many common reptile species are fire
56 1319 specialists? A replicated natural experiment highlights the predictive weakness of a fire
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 1320 succession model. *Biol Conserv* **141**, 460-471.
4
5 1321 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2007.10.016>).
6
7 1322
8
9 1323 132. Driscoll, D. A., Smith, A. L., Blight, S. & Maindonald, J. 2012 Reptile responses to fire
10 1324 and the risk of post-disturbance sampling bias. *Biodivers Conserv* **21**, 1607-1625.
11
12 1325 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-012-0267-5>).
13
14
15 1326
16 1327 133. Smith, A. L., Bull, C. M. & Driscoll, D. A. 2013 Successional specialization in a reptile
17 1328 community cautions against widespread planned burning and complete fire suppression. *J*
18 1329 *Appl Ecol* **50**, 1178-1186. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12119>).
19
20
21
22 1330
23
24 1331 134. Pianka, E. R. 1989 Desert lizard diversity: additional comments and some data. *Am Nat*
25 1332 **134**, 344-364. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1086/284985>).
26
27
28 1333
29
30 1334 135. Laver, R. J., Nielsen, S. V., Rosauer, D. F. & Oliver, P. M. 2017 Trans-biome diversity
31 1335 in Australian grass-specialist lizards (Diplodactylidae: *Strophurus*). *Mol Phyl Evol* **115**, 62-
32 1336 70. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2017.07.015>).
33
34
35
36 1337
37 1338 136. Kelly, L. T., Nimmo, D. G., Spence-Bailey, L. M., Clarke, M. F. & Bennett, A. F. 2010
38 1339 The short-term responses of small mammals to wildfire in semiarid mallee shrubland,
39 1340 Australia. *Wildl Res* **37**, 293-300. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1071/WR10016>).
40
41
42
43 1341
44
45 1342 137. Kelly, L. T., Nimmo, D. G., Spence-Bailey, L. M., Haslem, A., Watson, S. J., Clarke, M.
46 1343 F. & Bennett, A. F. 2011 Influence of fire history on small mammal distributions: insights
47 1344 from a 100-year post-fire chronosequence. *Divers Distrib* **17**, 462-473.
48
49 1345 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1472-4642.2011.00754.x>).
50
51
52 1346
53
54 1347 138. Carbone, L. M. & Aguilar, R. 2021 Abiotic and biotic interactions as drivers of plant
55 1348 reproduction in response to fire frequency. *Arthropod-Plant Interact* **15**, 83-94.
56
57 1349 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11829-020-09792-3>).
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 1350
4
5 1351 139. García, Y., Castellanos, M. C. & Pausas, J. G. 2016 Fires can benefit plants by
6 1352 disrupting antagonistic interactions. *Oecologia* **182**, 1165-1173.
7
8 1353 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-016-3733-z>).
9
10 1354
11
12 1355 140. Baeza, J., Raventos, J. & Escarre, A. (2002). *Ulex parviflorus* germination after
13 1356 experimental burning: effects of temperature and soil depth. In 'Third International Workshop
14 1357 on Fire Ecology', Oct 22-26 2001, Banyuls-Sur-Mer, France. (Eds. L. Trabaud & R. Prodon)
15 1358 pp. 83-91. (Backhuys Publishers: Leiden, The Netherlands.)
16
17
18
19 1359
20
21 1360 141. Pausas, J. G., Alessio, G. A., Moreira, B. & Corcobado, G. 2012 Fires enhance
22 1361 flammability in *Ulex parviflorus*. *New Phytol* **193**, 18-23.
23 1362 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-8137.2011.03945.x>).
24
25
26
27 1363
28
29 1364 142. Turner, M. G., Braziunas, K. H., Hansen, W. D., Hoecker, T. J., Rammer, W.,
30 1365 Ratajczak, Z., Westerling, A. L. & Seidl, R. 2022 The magnitude, direction, and tempo of
31 1366 forest change in Greater Yellowstone in a warmer world with more fire. *Ecol Monogr* **92**,
32 1367 e01485. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1002/ecm.1485>).
33
34
35
36
37 1368
38
39 1369 143. Franklin, T. L. & Laven, R. D. Fire influences on central Rocky Mountain lodgepole
40 1370 pine stand structure and composition. In 'High-intensity fire in wildlifands: management
41 1371 challenges and options: Proceedings, 17th Tall Timbers fire ecology conference', 1991,
42 1372 Tallahassee, Florida, United States of America. (Ed. S. M. Hermann) pp. 183-196. (Tall
43 1373 Timbers Research Station.)
44
45
46
47
48 1374
49
50 1375 144. Perry, D. A. & Lotan, J. E. 1979 A model of fire selection for serotiny in lodgepole pine.
51 1376 *Evolution* **33**, 958-968. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1558-5646.1979.tb04749.x>).
52
53
54 1377
55
56 1378 145. Anderson, M. D. 2003 *Pinus contorta* var. *latifolia*. In: Fire Effects Information System.
57 1379 United States of America U. S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, Rocky Mountain
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 1380 Research Station, Fire Sciences Laboratory. Viewed 21 May 2024, <<https://www.fs.usda.gov>
4 1381 /database/feis/plants/tree/pinconl/all.html>.
5
6
7 1382
8
9 1383 146. Turner, M. G., Braziunas, K. H., Hansen, W. D. & Harvey, B. J. 2019 Short-interval
10 1384 severe fire erodes the resilience of subalpine lodgepole pine forests. *PNAS Nexus* **116**, 11319-
11 1385 11328. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1902841116>).
12
13
14
15 1386
16 1387 147. Schoennagel, T., Turner, M. G. & Romme, W. H. 2003 The influence of fire interval
17 1388 and serotiny on postfire Lodgepole Pine density in Yellowstone National Parks. *Ecology* **84**,
18 1389 2967-2978. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1890/02-0277>).
19
20
21
22 1390
23
24 1391 148. Westerling, A. L., Turner, M. G., Smithwick, E. A. H., Romme, W. H. & Ryan, M. G.
25 1392 2011 Continued warming could transform Greater Yellowstone fire regimes by mid-21st
26 1393 century. *PNAS Nexus* **108**, 13165-13170. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1110199108>).
27
28
29
30 1394
31
32 1395 149. Sullivan, J. 1995 *Tamiasciurus hudsonicus*. In: Fire Effects Information System. United
33 1396 States of America U. S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, Rocky Mountain
34 1397 Research Station, Fire Sciences Laboratory. Viewed 30 May 2024,
35 1398 <www.fs.usda.gov/database/feis/animals/mammal/tahu/all.html>.
36
37
38
39 1399
40
41 1400 150. Berris, K. K., Barth, M., Welz, T. & Crowley, G. M. 2012 Kangaroo Island Glossy
42 1401 Black-cockatoo *Calyptorhynchus lathami halmaturinus*. In *The Action Plan for Australian*
43 1402 *Birds 2020* (ed. S. T. G. a. G. B. Baker), pp. 391-394. Victoria, Australia, CSIRO Publishing.
44
45
46
47 1403
48
49 1404 151. Cameron, M., Castley, G., Teixeira, D., Menkhorst, P. W. & Garnett, S. T. 2021 South-
50 1405 eastern Glossy Black-cockatoo *Calyptorhynchus lathami lathami*. In *The Action Plan for*
51 1406 *Australian Birds 2020* (ed. S. T. G. a. G. B. Baker), pp. 395-398. Melbourne, CSIRO
52 1407 Publishing.
53
54
55
56 1408
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 1409 152. Cameron, M. & Cunningham, R. B. 2006 Habitat selection at multiple spatial scales by
4 1410 foraging Glossy Black-cockatoos. *Austral Ecol* **31**, 597-607.
5 1411 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1442-9993.2006.01591.x>).
6
7 1412
8
9 1413
10 1414 153. Delzoppo, N. A., Berris, K. K., Teixeira, D. & van Rensburg, B. 2021 The impact of fire
11 1415 on the quality of Drooping sheoak (*Allocasuarina verticillata*) cones for the endangered
12 1416 Kangaroo Island Glossy Black-cockatoo (*Calyptorhynchus lathami halmaturinus*). *Glob Ecol*
13 1417 *Conserv* **28**, e01645. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2021.e01645>).
14
15 1418
16 1419 154. Chapman, T. F. 2007 Foods of the Glossy Black-cockatoo: *Calyptorhynchus lathami*.
17 1420 *Aust Field Ornithol* **24**, 30-36.
18
19 1421
20 1422 155. Lamont, B. B., Hanley, M. E., Groom, P. K. & He, T. 2016 Bird pollinators, seed
21 1423 storage and cockatoo granivores explain large woody fruits as best seed defense in *Hakea*.
22 1424 *Perspect Plant Ecol Evol Syst* **21**, 55-77. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ppees.2016.05.002>).
23
24 1425
25 1426 156. Heyes, S. D., Morgan, J. W., Sinclair, S. J., Walker, Z. C. & Hoebee, S. E. 2023 Pre-
26 1427 dispersal seed-predation affects fruit crop and seed fitness in a highly fragmented savanna
27 1428 tree. *Aust J Bot* **71**, 434-442. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1071/BT23011>).
28
29 1429
30 1430 157. Berris, K. K., Jones, R. M. H., Kok, X., McCafferty, A. K. J., Skirrow, J. K. & Mooney,
31 1431 T. 2022 The effect of inter-fire interval and fire severity on seedling germination and
32 1432 resprouting in *Allocasuarina verticillata*. *Aust J Bot* **70**, 384-395.
33 1433 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1071/BT22016>).
34
35 1434
36 1435 158. Sundell, J., Eccard, J. A., Tiilikainen, R. & Ylönen, H. 2003 Predation rate, prey
37 1436 preference and predator switching: experiments on voles and weasels. *Oikos* **101**, 615-623.
38 1437 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1034/j.1600-0706.2003.12264.x>).
39
40 1438
41 1439 159. Wells, B. K., Santora, J. A., Henderson, M. J., Warzybok, P., Jahncke, J., Bradley, R.
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 1440 Environmental conditions and prey-switching by a seabird predator impact juvenile salmon
4 survival. *J Mar Syst* **174**, 54-63. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmarsys.2017.05.008>).
- 5 1441
6
7 1442
8
9 1443 160. Pepper, J. W. 1991 A new food source for the Glossy Black-Cockatoo. *S Aust Ornithol*
10 **31**, 144-145.
11 1444
12
13 1445
14
15 1446 161. Swartz, M. T., Ferster, B., Vulinec, K. & Paulson, G. 2015 Measuring Regal Fritillary
16 butterfly (*Speyeria idalia*) habitat requirements in south-central Pennsylvania: implications
17 1447 for the conservation of an imperiled butterfly. *Northeast Nat* **22**, 812-829.
18 1448 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1656/045.022.0414>).
- 19 1449
20 1450
21
22 1451 162. Courard-Hauri, D., Wick, A. A., Kneubuhler, L. K. & Summerville, K. S. 2006 Patch-
23 scale movement dynamics in the Iowa grassland butterflies *Speyeria cybele* and *Megisto*
24 1452 *cymela* (Lepidoptera: Nymphalidae). *Great Lakes Entomol* **39**, 184-199.
25 1453 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.22543/0090-0222.2164>).
- 26 1454
27
28 1455
29 1456 163. Hiroyoshi, S. & Reddy, G. V. P. 2018 Field and laboratory studies on the ecology,
30 1457 reproduction, and adult diapause of the Asian Comma butterfly, *Polygonia c-aureum* L.
31 1458 (Lepidoptera: Nymphalidae). *Insects* **9**, 169. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.3390/insects9040169>).
- 32 1459
33
34 1460 164. McCullough, K., Albanese, G. & Haukos, D. A. 2017 Novel observations of larval fire
35 1461 survival, feeding behavior, and host plant use in the Regal Fritillary, *Speyeria idalia* (Drury)
36 1462 (Nymphalidae). *J Lepid Soc* **71**, 146-152. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.18473/lepi.71i3.a4>).
- 37 1463
38
39 1464 165. Maron, J. L. 1998 Insect herbivory above- and belowground: individual and joint effects
40 1465 on plant fitness. *Ecology* **79**, 1281-1293. (DOI:[https://doi.org/10.1890/0012-9658\(1998\)079\[1281:IHAABI\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1890/0012-9658(1998)079[1281:IHAABI]2.0.CO;2)).
- 41 1466
42
43 1467
44
45 1468 166. Moranz, R. A., Debinski, D. M., McGranahan, D. A., Engle, D. M. & Miller, J. R. 2012
46 1469 Untangling the effects of fire, grazing, and land-use legacies on grassland butterfly
- 47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 1470 communities. *Biodivers Conserv* **21**, 2719-2746. (DOI:[https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-012-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-012-0330-2)
4 1471 [0330-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-012-0330-2)).
- 5
6
7 1472
- 8
9 1473 167. Moranz, R. A., Fuhlendorf, S. D. & Engle, D. M. 2014 Making sense of a prairie
10 1474 butterfly paradox: the effects of grazing, time since fire, and sampling period on Regal
11 1475 Fritillary abundance. *Biol Conserv* **173**, 32-41.
12
13 1476 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2014.03.003>).
- 14
15
16 1477
- 17
18 1478 168. Adamidis, G. C., Swartz, M. T., Zografou, K. & Sewall, B. J. 2019 Prescribed fire
19 1479 maintains host plants of a rare grassland butterfly. *Sci Rep* **9**, 16826.
20
21 1480 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-53400-1>).
- 22
23
24 1481
- 25
26 1482 169. Vogel, J. A., Debinski, D. M., Koford, R. R. & Miller, J. R. 2007 Butterfly responses to
27 1483 prairie restoration through fire and grazing. *Biol Conserv* **140**, 78-90.
28
29 1484 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2007.07.027>).
- 30
31
32 1485
- 33 1486 170. Vogel, J. A., Koford, R. R. & Debinski, D. M. 2010 Direct and indirect responses of
34 1487 tallgrass prairie butterflies to prescribed burning. *J Insect Conserv* **14**, 663-677.
35
36 1488 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10841-010-9295-1>).
- 37
38
39 1489
- 40
41 1490 171. Latham, R. E., Zercher, D., McElhenny, P., Mooreside, P. & Ferster, B. 2007 The role
42 1491 of disturbance in habitat restoration and management for the Eastern Regal Fritillary
43 1492 (*Speyeria idalia idalia*) at a military installation in Pennsylvania. *Ecol Restor* **25**, 103-111.
44
45 1493 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.3368/er.25.2.103>).
- 46
47
48 1494
- 49
50 1495 172. Rudolph, D. C., Ely, C. A., Schaefer, R. R., Williamson, J. H. & Thill, R. E. 2006 The
51 1496 Diana Fritillary (*Speyeria diana*) and Great Spangled Fritillary (*S. cybele*): dependence on
52 1497 fire in the Ouachita Mountains of Arkansas. *J Lepid Soc* **60**, 218-226.
53
54
55
56 1498
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 1499 173. Henderson, R. A., Meunier, J. & Holoubek, N. S. 2018 Disentangling effects of fire,
4 1500 habitat, and climate on an endangered prairie-specialist butterfly. *Biol Conserv* **218**, 41-48.
5 1501 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2017.10.034>).
6
7
8
9 1502
10
11 1503 174. Shuey, J., Jacquart, E., Orr, S., Becker, F., Nyberg, A., Littiken, R., Anchor, T. &
12 1504 Luchik, D. 2016 Landscape-scale response to local habitat restoration in the regal fritillary
13 1505 butterfly (*Speyeria idalia*) (Lepidoptera: Nymphalidae). *J Insect Conserv* **20**, 773-780.
14 1506 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10841-016-9908-4>).
15
16
17
18 1507
19
20 1508 175. Kwon, T.-S., Kim, S.-S., Lee, C. M. & Jung, S. J. 2013 Changes of butterfly
21 1509 communities after forest fire. *J Asia Pac Entomol* **16**, 361-367.
22 1510 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aspen.2013.04.010>).
23
24
25
26 1511
27
28 1512 176. Kopper, B., Charlton, R. & Margolies, D. 2000 Oviposition site selection by the Regal
29 1513 Fritillary, *Speyeria idalia*, as affected by proximity of violet host plants. *J Insect Behav* **13**.
30 1514 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1007887809621>).
31
32
33
34 1515
35 1516 177. Hill, R. I., Rush, C. E. & Mayberry, J. 2018 Larval food limitation in a *Speyeria*
36 1517 butterfly (Nymphalidae): how many butterflies can be supported? *Insects* **9**, 179.
37 1518 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.3390/insects9040179>).
38
39
40
41 1519
42
43 1520 178. Herzig, A. L. & Skema, C. 2004 Feeding behavior and performance of a Rabbitbrush
44 1521 leaf-beetle (*Trirhabda lewisii*) feeding on *Chrysothamnus nauseosus* regrowth after fire. *West*
45 1522 *N Am Nat* **64**, 249-256.
46
47
48
49 1523
50 1524 179. Kay, A. D., Schade, J. D., Ogdahl, M., Wesslerle, E. O. & Hobbie, S. E. 2007 Fire effects
51 1525 on insect herbivores in an oak savanna: the role of light and nutrients. *Ecol Entomol* **32**, 754-
52 1526 761. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2311.2007.00925.x>).
53
54
55
56 1527
57
58 1528 180. Stancă-Moise, C., Moise, G., Rotaru, M., Vonica, G. & Sanislau, D. 2023 Study on the
59 1529 ecology, biology and ethology of the invasive species *Corythucha arcuata* Say, 1832

- 1
2
3 1530 (Heteroptera: Tingidae), a danger to *Quercus spp.* in the climatic conditions of the city of
4 1531 Sibiu, Romania. *Forests* **14**, 1278. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.3390/f14061278>).
- 6
7 1532
8
9 1533 181. Nadal, M. & Flexas, J. 2018 Chapter 17 - Mesophyll conductance to CO₂ diffusion:
10 1534 effects of drought and opportunities for improvement. In *Water scarcity and sustainable*
11 1535 *agriculture in semiarid environment: tools, strategies, and challenges for woody crops* (eds.
12 1536 I. F. García Tejero & V. H. Durán Zuazo), pp. 403-438. London, United Kingdom, Elsevier.
- 16
17 1537
18 1538 182. Tirmenstein, D. 1999 *Ericameria nauseosa*. In: Fire Effects Information System. United
19 1539 States of America U. S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, Rocky Mountain Research
20 1540 Station, Fire Sciences Laboratory. Viewed 22 January 2024,
21 1541 <<https://www.fs.usda.gov/database/feis/plants/shrub/erinau/all.html>>.
- 25
26 1542
27 1543 183. Gucker, C. L. 2011 *Quercus macrocarpa*. In Fire Effects Information System. United
28 1544 States of America U. S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, Rocky Mountain Research
29 1545 Station, Fire Sciences Laboratory. Viewed 22 January 2024,
30 1546 <<https://www.fs.usda.gov/database/feis/plants/tree/quemac/all.html>>.
- 34
35 1547
36 1548 184. Colautti, R. I., Ricciardi, A., Grigorovich, I. A. & MacIsaac, H. J. 2004 Is invasion
37 1549 success explained by the enemy release hypothesis? *Ecol Lett* **7**, 721-733.
38 1550 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2004.00616.x>).
- 42
43 1551
44 1552 185. Warchola, N., Bastianelli, C., Schultz, C. B. & Crone, E. E. 2015 Fire increases ant-
45 1553 tending and survival of the Fender's Blue butterfly larvae. *J Insect Conserv* **19**, 1063-1073.
46 1554 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10841-015-9822-1>).
- 49
50 1555
51 1556 186. Schultz, C. B. & Crone, E. E. 1998 Burning prairie to restore butterfly habitat: a
52 1557 modeling approach to management tradeoffs for the Fender's Blue. *Restor Ecol* **6**, 244-252.
53 1558 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1526-100X.1998.00637.x>).
- 56
57 1559
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 1560 187. Warchola, N., Crone, E. E. & Schultz, C. B. 2018 Balancing ecological costs and
4 1561 benefits of fire for population viability of disturbance-dependent butterflies. *J Appl Ecol* **55**,
5 1562 800-809. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12983>).
6
7
8
9 1563
10
11 1564 188. Schultz, C. B., Hammond, P. C. & Wilson, M. V. 2003 Biology of the Fender's Blue
12 1565 butterfly (*Icaricia icarioides fenderi* Macy), an endangered species of western Oregon native
13 1566 prairies. *Nat Areas J* **23**, 61-71.
14
15
16 1567
17
18 1568 189. Kaye, T. N. 1999 Obligate insect pollination of a rare plant, *Lupinus sulphureus ssp.*
19 1569 *kincaidii*. *Northwest Sci* **73**, 50-52.
20
21
22 1570
23
24 1571 190. Petix, M. I. & Bahm, M. A. 2017 Kincaid's lupine and habitat monitoring at Fir Butte.
25 1572 Report to the Bureau of Land Management, Eugene District. Institute for Applied Ecology.
26 1573 (Institute for Applied Ecology: United States of America.) Viewed 30 January 2024,
27 1574 <[https://appliedeco.org/report/kincaids-lupine-lupinus-oreganus-and-habitat-monitoring-at-](https://appliedeco.org/report/kincaids-lupine-lupinus-oreganus-and-habitat-monitoring-at-fir-butte-3/)
28 1575 [fir-butte-3/](https://appliedeco.org/report/kincaids-lupine-lupinus-oreganus-and-habitat-monitoring-at-fir-butte-3/)>.
29
30
31
32
33 1576
34
35 1577 191. Pierce, N. E., Braby, M. F., Heath, A., Lohman, D. J., Mathew, J., Rand, D. B. &
36 1578 Travassos, M. A. 2002 The ecology and evolution of ant association in the Lycaenidae
37 1579 (Lepidoptera). *Annu Rev Entomol* **47**, 733-771.
38 1580 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.ento.47.091201.145257>).
39
40
41
42
43 1581
44 1582 192. Meyer, R. 2006 *Lupinus perennis*. In: Fire Effects Information System. United States of
45 1583 America U.S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, Rocky Mountain Research Station,
46 1584 Fire Sciences Laboratory. Viewed 31 January 2024,
47 1585 <<https://www.fs.usda.gov/database/feis/plants/forb/lupper/all.html>>.
48
49
50
51
52 1586
53
54 1587 193. Reeves, S. L. 2006 *Lupinus latifolius*. In: Fire Effects Information System. United States
55 1588 of America U.S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, Rocky Mountain Research
56 1589 Station, Fire Sciences Laboratory. Viewed 31 January 2024,
57 1590 <<https://www.fs.usda.gov/database/feis/plants/forb/luplat/all.html>>.
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 1591
4
5 1592 194. Ross, G. N. 1966 Life-history studies on Mexican butterflies. IV. The ecology and
6
7 1593 ethology of *Anatole rossi*, a myrmecophilous Metalmark (Lepidoptera: Riodinidae). *Ann*
8
9 1594 *Entomol Soc Am* **59**, 985-1004. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1093/aesa/59.5.985>).
- 10
11 1595
12 1596 195. Narbona, E. & Dirzo, R. 2010 A reassessment of the function of floral nectar in *Croton*
13
14 1597 *suberosus* (Euphorbiaceae): a reward for plant defenders and pollinators. *Am J Bot* **97**, 672-
15
16 1598 679. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.3732/ajb.0900259>).
- 17
18 1599
19
20 1600 196. Fadini, R. F. & Lima, A. P. 2012 Fire and host abundance as determinants of the
21
22 1601 distribution of three congener and sympatric mistletoes in an Amazonian savanna. *Biotropica*
23
24 1602 **44**, 27-34. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-7429.2011.00773.x>).
- 25
26 1603
27
28 1604 197. Start, A. N. 2011 Fire responses and survival strategies of mistletoes (Loranthaceae) in
29
30 1605 an arid environment in Western Australia. *Aust J Bot* **59**, 533-542.
31 1606 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1071/BT11054>).
- 32
33 1607
34
35 1608 198. Start, A. N. 2013 Mistletoe flora (Loranthaceae and Santalaceae) of the Kimberley, a
36
37 1609 tropical region in Western Australia, with particular reference to fire. *Aust J Bot* **61**, 309-321.
38 1610 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1071/BT13021>).
- 39
40
41 1611
42
43 1612 199. Muche, M., Muasya, A. M. & Tsegay, B. A. 2022 Biology and resource acquisition of
44
45 1613 mistletoes, and the defense responses of host plants. *Ecol Process* **11**, 24.
46 1614 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13717-021-00355-9>).
- 47
48 1615
49
50 1616 200. Gill, A. M. 1996 How fires affect biodiversity. In "*Fire and biodiversity : the effects and*
51
52 1617 *effectiveness of fire management*" *Biodiversity series; paper no. 8* (ed. Victorian National
53
54 1618 Parks Association), p. 278. Australia, Department of the Environment, Sport and Territories,
55 1619 Biodiversity Unit.
- 56
57
58 1620
59
60

- 1
2
3 1621 201. Oliveira Silva, G., Carvalho da Silva, R., Bezerra Souza, F., Aurélio Campos Aguiar, B.,
4 1622 Cardoso Lopes, V. & Bezerra de Souza, P. 2022 Dynamics of a woody community in a
5 1623 cerrado *sensu stricto* area in space and time. *Floresta* **52**, 342-350.
6
7 1624 (DOI:[10.5380/RF.v52i2.80815](https://doi.org/10.5380/RF.v52i2.80815)).
8
9
10 1625
11
12 1626 202. Richardson, K. C. & Wooller, R. D. 1988 The alimentary-tract of a specialist frugivore,
13 1627 the mistletoebird, *Dicaeum-hirundinaceum*, in relation to its diet. *Aust J Zool* **36**, 373-382.
14 1628 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1071/ZO9880373>).
15
16 1629
17
18 1630 203. Stevens, H. C. & Watson, D. M. 2022 Interacting impacts of drought and fire on bird
19 1631 populations - insights from a long-term study in the Warrumbungles. *Aust Zool* **42**, 608-630.
20 1632 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.7882/AZ.2022.036>).
21
22 1633
23
24 1634 204. Govaert, L., Fronhofer, E. A., Lion, S., Eizaguirre, C., Bonte, D., Egas, M., Hendry, A.
25 1635 P., De Brito Martins, A., Melián, C. J., Raeymaekers, J. A. M., et al. 2019 Eco-evolutionary
26 1636 feedbacks - theoretical models and perspectives. *Funct. Ecol.* **33**, 13-30.
27 1637 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2435.13241>).
28
29 1638
30
31 1639 205. Brunner, F. S., Deere, J. A., Egas, M., Eizaguirre, C. & Raeymaekers, J. A. M. 2019 The
32 1640 diversity of eco-evolutionary dynamics: comparing the feedbacks between ecology and
33 1641 evolution across scales. *Funct. Ecol.* **33**, 7-12. (DOI:[https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-](https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2435.13268)
34 1642 [2435.13268](https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2435.13268)).
35
36 1643
37
38 1644 206. DeLong, J. P., Forbes, V. E., Galic, N., Gibert, J. P., Laport, R. G., Phillips, J. S. &
39 1645 Vavra, J. M. 2016 How fast is fast? Eco-evolutionary dynamics and rates of change in
40 1646 populations and phenotypes. *Ecol Evol* **6**, 573-581. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.1899>).
41
42 1647
43
44 1648 207. Carroll, S. P., Hendry, A. P., Reznick, D. N. & Fox, C. W. 2007 Evolution on ecological
45 1649 time-scales. *Funct. Ecol.* **21**, 387-393. (DOI:[https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2435.2007.01289.x)
46 1650 [2435.2007.01289.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2435.2007.01289.x)).
47
48 1651
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 1652 208. Hairston Jr, N. G., Ellner, S. P., Geber, M. A., Yoshida, T. & Fox, J. A. 2005 Rapid
4 1653 evolution and the convergence of ecological and evolutionary time. *Ecol Lett* **8**, 1114-1127.
5 1654 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2005.00812.x>).
6
7
8
9 1655
10
11 1656 209. Zamorano, L. S., Gompert, Z., Fronhofer, E. A., Feder, J. L. & Nosil, P. 2023 A
12 1657 stabilizing eco-evolutionary feedback loop in the wild. *Curr Biol* **33**, 3272-3278.
13 1658 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2023.06.056>).
14
15
16 1659
17
18 1660 210. Cortez, M. H. 2018 Genetic variation determines which feedbacks drive and alter
19 1661 predator–prey eco-evolutionary cycles. *Ecol Monogr* **88**, 353-371.
20 1662 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1002/ecm.1304>).
21
22
23
24 1663
25
26 1664 211. Carbone, L. M., Tavella, J., Marquez, V., Ashworth, L., Pausas, J. G. & Aguilar, R.
27 1665 2024 Fire effects on pollination and plant reproduction: a quantitative review. *Ann Bot*.
28 1666 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1093/aob/mcae033>).
29
30
31 1667
32
33 1668 212. D'Antonio, C. M. & Vitousek, P. M. 1992 Biological invasions by exotic grasses, the
34 1669 grass/fire cycle, and global change. *Annu Rev Ecol Evol Syst* **23**, 63-87.
35 1670 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.es.23.110192.000431>).
36
37
38
39 1671
40
41 1672 213. Liu, Y., Zhang, Y., Nowak, R. S. & Dimeyeva, L. 2013 Diaspore characteristics and
42 1673 ecological adaptation of *Bromus tectorum* L. from different distribution regions. *JAL* **5**, 310-
43 1674 323. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s40333-013-0171-1>).
44
45
46 1675
47
48 1676 214. Fenesi, A., Saura-Mas, S., Blank, R. R., Kozma, A., Lózer, B.-M. & Ruprecht, E. 2016
49 1677 Enhanced fire-related traits may contribute to the invasiveness of downy Brome (*Bromus*
50 1678 *tectorum*). *Invasive plant sci. manag* **9**, 182-194. (DOI:10.1614/IPSM-D-16-00006.1).
51
52
53
54 1679
55
56 1680 215. McPeck, S. J., Bronstein, J. L. & McPeck, M. A. 2022 Eco-evolutionary feedbacks
57 1681 among pollinators, herbivores, and their plant resources. *Evolution* **76**, 1287-1300.
58 1682 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/evo.14492>).
59
60

- 1
2
3 1683
4
5 1684 216. de Andreazzi, C. S., Guimarães, P. R. & Melián, C. J. 2018 Eco-evolutionary feedbacks
6 1685 promote fluctuating selection and long-term stability of antagonistic networks. *Proc Biol Sci*
7 1686 **285**. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2017.2596>).
- 8
9
10 1687
11
12 1688 217. Loeuille, N. 2019 Eco-evolutionary dynamics in a disturbed world: implications for the
13 1689 maintenance of ecological networks. *F1000Res* **8**, 97.
14 1690 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.15629.1>).
- 15
16
17
18 1691
19
20 1692 218. Hurteau, M. D., Liang, S., Westerling, A. L. & Wiedinmyer, C. 2019 Vegetation-fire
21 1693 feedback reduces projected area burned under climate change. *Sci Rep* **9**, 2838.
22 1694 (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-39284-1>).
- 23
24
25
26 1695
27
28 1696 219. Jaureguiberry, P. & Díaz, S. 2023 A three-dimensional approach to general plant fire
29 1697 syndromes. *Funct. Ecol.* **37**, 2143-2158. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2435.14272>).
- 30
31
32 1698
33
34 1699 220. Kerby, J. D., Fuhlendorf, S. D. & Engle, D. M. 2007 Landscape heterogeneity and fire
35 1700 behavior: scale-dependent feedback between fire and grazing processes. *Landsc Ecol* **22**,
36 1701 507-516. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-006-9039-5>).
- 37
38
39 1702
40
41 1703 221. Powell, J., Martin, B., Dreitz, V. J. & Allred, B. W. 2018 Grazing preferences and
42 1704 vegetation feedbacks of the fire-grazing interaction in the northern Great Plains. *Range Ecol*
43 1705 *Manag* **71**, 45-52. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rama.2017.09.003>).
- 44
45
46
47 1706
48
49 1707 222. Benkman, C. W. 2013 Biotic interaction strength and the intensity of selection. *Ecol Lett*
50 1708 **16**, 1054-1060. (DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.12138>).
- 51
52
53 1709
54
55 1710
56
57
58
59
60

1711 **Figures**

1712
1713 **Figure 1** Plant and animal morphological, behavioural, and reproductive traits involved in
1714 specialised plant-animal interactions in fire-prone ecosystems. Points indicate traits identified
1715 from the literature as being involved in different types of interactions. The relative potential
1716 for selection to act on traits and feed back into ecological dynamics is signified by the size of
1717 the points: small points indicate traits likely under weak selection and large points indicate

1
2
3 1718 traits potentially under strong selection. Environmental variation influences these interactions
4
5 1719 and the fire regime by controlling habitat structure, connectivity, and aridity. The fire regime
6
7 1720 controls the environment by consuming vegetation and influencing recruitment and mortality
8
9 1721 processes in plants and animals. Plant and animal traits, particularly plant post-fire
10
11 1722 reproductive mode and morphology, and plant consumption behaviours in animals are likely
12
13 1723 to feed back into the environment and fire regime. For example, herbivory affects habitat
14
15 1724 connectedness which in turn affects the size, patchiness, and intensity of fires, feeding back
16
17 1725 into population dynamics of herbivores. Pollinators affect habitat structure by influencing
18
19 1726 flowering season, rate of seed set and, therefore, the potential for plant recruitment. This
20
21 1727 feeds back into the fire regime by influencing biomass and post-fire succession with
22
23 1728 subsequent influences on fire frequency.
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60